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List of abbreviations

CA	Cellulose Acetate
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
FDCA	2,5-Furandicarboxylic acid
HMF	5-hydroxymethylfurfural
kWh	Kilowatt hour
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OPEC	<i>Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries</i>
PA	Polyamide
<i>PBAT</i>	<i>Polybutylene adipate terephthalate</i>
PBS	Polybutylene succinate
PBT	Polybutylene terephthalate
PE	Polyethylene
PEF	Polyethylene 2,5-furandicarboxylate
PET	Polyethylene terephthalate
PHA	Polyhydroxyalkanoate
PLA	Polylactic acid
PP	Polypropylene
PTA	purified Terephthalic Acid
PTT	Polytrimethylene terephthalate
WFBR	Wageningen Food & Biobased Research

1. Introduction

The deliverable 1.1 “General Guidelines, barriers, and opportunities associated to industrial, macroeconomic, regulatory specifications” is the first deliverable of WP1, led by the University of Hohenheim and co-led by CTCPA. The objective of this deliverable is to provide a generic methodology common to all specifications from industry, bioeconomy, legislation, and standards including end of life solutions in order to develop an easy-to-use and practical tool to help sustainable packaging technologies to reach their best market. To reach this objective, the specifications will be expressed in a simple way through a decision tree that will be possibly exploited by software (future developments of WP1). The goal is then to translate the specifications into practical guidelines; this was achieved by extensive work on classifications of the various specifications related to packaging and packaged food products.

In the first sections project’s summary and a short description of works packages with tasks are given.

A systematic template for the inventory of industrial specifications, incl. material providers, packaging manufacturers, agro-food industry, and distribution (sections 2-5), and macroeconomic and regulatory constraints (sections 6-7) was developed. The general technological steps or property categories were listed, the sub-steps and the subcategories were also established (Figure 1).

A collection of possible technical and non-technical parameters for each technological step or property category is reported in the deliverable. This information was directly provided by the project partners and coordinated by the task leaders to ensure the specificity of the collected data. WP1 was expected to describe the current situation along the whole technological chain including:

- Specifications from packaging industries (Task leader: Wipak)
- Specifications from agro-industries (Task leader: Hipp)
- Specifications from retailers (Task leader: Lea Nature)
- Macroeconomic and regulatory barriers, legislation and end of life solutions (Task leader: UHOH)

1	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
2	technological step or property category	sub steps or sub categories	Partners involved	critical property 1	values or remarks	critical property 2	values or remarks	critical property 3	values or remarks	critical property 4
4	pretreatments	storage	All	specific conditions ?	no / yes (to be specified if yes)					
5		HR conditioning	All	specific conditions ?	no / yes (to be specified if yes)					
6		temperature conditioning	All	specific conditions ?	no / yes (to be specified if yes)					
8	plastic transformation	extrusion blown mono	Wipak	checked positively?	no / yes (detail equipment if yes)	Min transformation Temp	to be specified	Max transformation T	to be specified	Typical temperature profile
9		extrusion blown coex	Wipak	checked positively?	no / yes (detail equipment if yes)	Min transformation Temp	to be specified	Max transformation T	to be specified	Typical temperature profile
10		extrusion cast mono	Wipak	checked positively?	no / yes (detail equipment if yes)	Min transformation Temp	to be specified	Max transformation T	to be specified	Typical temperature profile
11		extrusion cast coex	Wipak	checked positively?	no / yes (detail equipment if yes)	Min transformation Temp	to be specified	Max transformation T	to be specified	Typical temperature profile
12		extrusion coating	Wipak	checked positively?	no / yes (detail equipment if yes)	Min transformation Temp	to be specified	Max transformation T	to be specified	Typical temperature profile
13		calendering	Wipak	checked positively?	no / yes (detail equipment if yes)	Min transformation Temp	to be specified	Max transformation T	to be specified	Typical temperature profile
14		injection moulding	Fuerst	checked positively?	no / yes (detail equipment if yes)	Min transformation Temp	to be specified	Max transformation T	to be specified	Typical temperature profile
15		/inmould labelling	Fuerst	checked positively?	no / yes (detail equipment if yes)	Min transformation Temp	to be specified	Max transformation T	to be specified	Typical temperature profile
20	printing on plastic	flexography	Wipak	checked positively?	no / yes (detail equipment if yes)	Inks and solvents possible	to be specified	Typical drying temperature	to be specified	
21		rotogravure	Wipak	checked positively?	no / yes (detail equipment if yes)	Inks and solvents possible	to be specified	Typical drying temperature	to be specified	
22		off-set	All	checked positively?	no / yes (detail equipment if yes)	Inks and solvents possible	to be specified	Typical drying temperature	to be specified	
23		digital	Wipak	checked positively?	no / yes (detail equipment if yes)	Inks and solvents possible	to be specified	Typical drying temperature	to be specified	
24		heat seal lacquering	Wipak	checked positively?	no / yes (detail equipment if yes)	Lacquers and solvents possible / not possible	to be specified	Typical drying temperature	to be specified	Typical application tempera
25		other lacquering (antifog, UV filter...)	Wipak	checked positively?	no / yes (detail equipment if yes)	possible / not possible	to be specified	Typical drying temperature	to be specified	Typical application tempera
26		cold seal lacquering	Wipak	checked positively?	no / yes (detail equipment if yes)	Lacquers and solvents possible / not possible	to be specified	Typical drying temperature	to be specified	Typical application tempera
30	lamination with plastic / paper	solvent based adhesive	Wipak	checked positively?	no / yes (detail equipment if yes)	Inks and solvents possible	to be specified	Typical drying temperature	to be specified	Typical application tempera
31		solvent free adhesive	Wipak	checked positively?	no / yes (detail equipment if yes)	Inks and solvents possible	to be specified	Typical drying temperature	to be specified	Typical application tempera
32		water based adhesive	Wipak	checked positively?	no / yes (detail equipment if yes)	Inks and solvents possible	to be specified	Typical drying temperature	to be specified	Typical application tempera
33		extrusion lamination	Wipak	checked positively?	no / yes (detail equipment if yes)	Min transformation Temp	to be specified	Max transformation T	to be specified	Typical temperature profile

Figure 1: An example of the common systematic template for the collection of specifications

2. Packaging industries

To define specifications from packaging industries, project partners used defined methodology and had several group meetings, calls to define classifications, critical points and data. Brainstorming mode was used to agree on a common form. The target of this template was to build a kind of filter able to calibrate needed processes, properties for materials, packaging solutions, future developments. Partners tried to utilize the expertise of different participants to define possible technological steps for packaging fabrication. It was clear that the definition of global steps and sub-steps is needed.

Global steps: pretreatments, plastic transformation, printing on plastic, lamination with plastic/paper, surface treatments and thin coating, post transformations of plastics. It was here logical for the group to think in terms of processes in a chronological way.

By sub-steps, partners tried to cover all possible transformation processes, available or not by members of the consortium, with the clear target to cover all process possibilities to make a packaging. Of course, the natural way was to go first to available technologies within the consortium. All these points are detailed in the template. The next step was to define critical properties for each sub-step, with definition of the nature of this critical property, and with values if possible, or with remarks.

It appeared quite rapidly that these properties should stay here general and not go too deep into details, as these key properties are not the same depending on raw materials. For example, a minimum transformation temperature is not the same for polyamide or for polyethylene. This is the reason why indications were kept more general at this level, more important was to indicate the key critical properties, process by process.

2.1 Categories of packaging processing operations

The following categories of packaging processing operations, classified on the basis of the successive technological steps realized to make packaging, have been defined:

- **Pretreatments:** many materials (at low TRL but also some materials on the market!) are not well defined concerning the necessary operations of preconditioning. Many materials need to realize a thermal treatment to remove volatiles (water, monomers and other low molecular weight compounds) BUT some new biomaterials need a conditioning in a humid environment in order to ensure their requirement in terms of water content: while the industrial practice is generally to *thermodesorb* polymers before processing, other biomaterials need at the contrary to be put in an adapted environment to *absorb* water. In addition to this, the removal of moisture from biopolyesters is recommended in order to prevent hydrolysis and therefore extend the shelf life of the granule;

- **Plastic transformation technologies:** the requirements of plastic rheologic properties depend directly on the types of plastic transformation technologies; for example injection technologies need low viscosities, while film blowing technology needs high viscosity coupled with adapted elongational viscosity, which is a specific property generally not addressed by its dedicated measurement but by film blowing feasibility tests. Commercial polymers have different “grades” adapted to these different plastic transformation technologies. Rheological properties are modulated by the formulation/ the polymer MW and polydispersity/chain branching / and the selection of processing conditions (mainly temperature but also the choice of equipment which has the effect on polymer shearing). Even with the use of these complex set of variables some polymers cannot access all the types of possible processing operations. An error often made by academic laboratories providing new polymer technologies is their claim of “new film technology”: most

of the time films made in laboratories are obtained by pressure under hot plates, which is the easiest way to process polymer materials but not the good one to make a film in industrial conditions. Another error of academic labs is the claim of a new injection technology or new extrusion technology at low production rates which have nothing to do with realistic cadency; using a laboratory material on an industrial line shows then degradation issues, too slow crystallization kinetics, misfit melt cohesion behavior, etc..

Another remark on the importance of a screening of processing technologies, is also the access to the variability of material properties as a function of the process type; as an example only industrial biorientation lines can confer a high polymer orientation; the interest to test it is both to evaluate the biorientation ability, but also to evaluate the potential high gain of mechanical and barrier properties associated to biorientation;

- **Plastic "S"** transformation technologies – Many packaging systems are not constituted by only one material, but by different material combinations. This is basically often forgotten by new polymer providers and most of the time by academic labs: a polymer material will have to be associated with other polymers providing sealing, barrier, mechanical, printable... complementary properties; the ability to be combined with other polymers by adapted technologies have then to be checked prior to market introduction;

- **Printing on plastics** – printing technologies can be the main of the time easily adapted to every kind of new material – then they not constitute the main barrier to easy access to the market for a new material. Nevertheless, it is better to have the knowledge of the best types of adapted inks and or ink technologies; in that purpose a preliminary set of printing tests is an advantage for the best market access of a new packaging material technology;

- **Lamination with plastic/paper** – Lamination needs very different characteristics of the material, depending on the substrate type and characteristics (porosity, rugosity) and depending on the (sub) type of lamination technology. It is then hard to define an absolute specification set of adapted properties, but at least it is good to be able to illustrate the use of lamination technology with a presentation of case studies and related set of optimized parameters;

- **Surface treatments and thin coating** – As opposed to printing technologies which are quite flexible thanks to the large possibilities of formulation, surface treatments, and thin coating technologies are less flexible; their compatibility with new material technologies and their eventual optimization routes need then to be tested before market access;

- **Post transformations of plastics** – Except concerning thermoforming, most of the operations listed in this category are not often used in industry; it is then not a priority to test them before introduction of new material on the market; on the other hand, it is worth mentioning the results of the tests have been done.

2.2 Subcategories of packaging processing operations

An exhaustive listing of the subcategories has been defined by the working group; they are listed in the table below:

Table 1: List of subcategories of packaging processing operations

Categories	Subcategories	Comments
pretreatments	storage	New practices related to bioplastics led us to define the dedicated subcategories of “storage” (some resins age quickly in room RH – T conditions), and of “HR conditioning” (some materials are better transformed with a slight hydration)
	HR conditioning	
	temperature conditioning	
plastic transformation	extrusion blown mono	All these transformation technologies involve properties of plastics at molten state, but with different requirements concerning the rheologic behavior, and including interfacial properties concerning co extrusion and co injection
	extrusion blown coex	
	extrusion cast mono	
	extrusion cast coex	
	extrusion coating	
	calendering	
	injection moulding	
	Inmould labeling	
	extrusion blow moulding	
	injection blow moulding	
printing on plastic	flexography	The choice was made to establish categories on the basis of the types of technologies; however, the classification of printing technologies involves also the chemical type of inks, their solvent type (water-based or solvent-based), and their mechanism and technology of drying and or crosslinking. This makes a wide field to consider; for a new material to put on the market it is also not possible to have the exhaustive overview of the material “printability” but minimum of investigations must be done, at least considering the most frequently used technologies and ink types
	rotogravure	
	off-set	
	digital	
	heat seal lacquering	
	Other lacquering (antifog, UV filter...)	
	cold seal lacquering	
lamination with plastic/paper	solvent-based adhesive	Adhesive based lamination technologies can be more or less performed on the big majority of materials. They do not constitute a real technical barrier; however, it is better to check their feasibility and particularly the feasibility of water-based technologies which are generally preferred for their better environmental fingerprint. Even better concerning environmental performance is the extrusion lamination which does not involve the use of solvents and or energy-consuming drying operations. The feasibility of extrusion lamination has then to be checked in priority; it raises the issue of adhesion capability of the layers associated
	solvent-free adhesive	
	water-based adhesive	
	extrusion lamination	
surface treatments and thin coating	oxidative plasma	These treatments confer specific surface properties (wetting and adhesion) to the original materials and or barrier properties. They are theoretically possible to be applied on all types of material but the academic and industry expertise is in reality very limited: corona has
	specific plasma	
	corona	
	metallization	
	CxHy coating	
	SiOx coating	

	Alox coating	<p>been designed for polyolefins and most of the other treatments are correctly optimized for PET...</p> <p>For the other polymers, the parameters of polyolefins or PET are generally taken or poorly adapted.</p> <p>Then for a new material to be put on the market, it cannot be asked to make better... but a big margin of improvement of the technologies should be found by working on the adaptation of the processing conditions of surface treatments. Considering the combination between Furstgroup SiOx coating technology and the material innovations of Novamont, Avalon, and Natureplast, Mypack project will have the opportunity to illustrate the need for optimization of such a surface functionalization technology</p>
post transformations of plastics	thermoforming	
	EB curing (cross-linking)	
	mechanical perforation	
	laser perforation	
	slitting	
	Orientation (mono or bi)	
	Labeling	

2.3 Inventory of critical properties

A very systematic work has been realized through small working groups to fill the critical properties related to the subcategories (Table 2).

General comments: It appeared quite rapidly that these properties should stay here general and not go too deep into details, as these key properties are not the same depending on raw materials. For example, a minimum transformation temperature is not the same for polyamide or for polyethylene. This is the reason why we kept indications more general at this level, more important was to indicate the key critical properties, process by process.

Table 2: Critical properties of subcategories of packaging processing operations

Subcategories	Comments on the critical properties selected
storage	For all these subcategories, when specific conditions are required, they must be specified
HR conditioning	
temperature conditioning	
extrusion blown mono	For all these subcategories, the central point is to check if feasibility tests have been performed; if yes, the data test should be provided, specifying (i) the equipment used for the tests, (ii) the minimum and maximum temperatures of transformation, and the typical temperature profile to be used
extrusion blown coex	
extrusion cast mono	
extrusion cast coex	
extrusion coating	
calendering	
injection moulding	

Inmould labeling	
flexography	For all these subcategories, the central point is to check if feasibility tests have been performed ; if yes, the data test should be provided, specifying (i) the equipment used for the tests, (ii) the inks and solvents possible and not possible to be used, and (iii) the typical drying temperature
rotogravure	
off-set	
digital	
heat seal lacquering	For all these subcategories, the central point is to check if feasibility tests have been performed ; if yes, the data test should be provided, specifying (i) the equipment used for the tests, (ii) the lacquers and solvents possible and not possible to be used, (iii) the typical application temperature, and (iv) the typical drying temperature
Other lacquering (antifog, UV filter...)	
cold seal lacquering	
solvent-based adhesive	For all these subcategories, the central point is to check if feasibility tests have been performed ; if yes, the data test should be provided, specifying (i) the equipment used for the tests, (ii) the adhesives and solvents possible and not possible to be used, (iii) the typical application temperature, (iv) the typical drying temperature, and (v) the type and maximum residual solvent content
solvent-free adhesive	
water-based adhesive	
extrusion lamination	For this subcategory, the central point is to check if feasibility tests have been performed if yes, the data test should be provided, specifying (i) the equipment used for the tests, (ii) the minimum and maximum temperatures of transformation, and the typical temperature profile to be used
oxidative plasma	For these subcategories the central point is to check if feasibility tests have been performed; if yes, the data test should be provided, specifying the equipment used for the tests
specific plasma	
corona	For this subcategory the central point is to check if feasibility tests have been performed; if yes, the data test should be provided, specifying the equipment used for the tests, the mini and maxi W/m ² and the mini and maxi surface tension in dyn
metallization	For this subcategory the central point is to check if feasibility tests have been performed; if yes, the data test should be provided, specifying the equipment used for the tests, and the mini and maxi optical density
CxHy coating	For these subcategories the central point is to check if feasibility tests have been performed; if yes, the data test should be provided, specifying the equipment used for the tests, and the mini and maxi thickness
SiOx coating	
Alox coating	
thermoforming	For this subcategory the central point is to check if feasibility tests have been performed; if yes, the data test should be provided, specifying the equipment used for the tests, the forming temperature/time range, the possible depth ratio, and the residual thickness depending of starting thickness / forming plate
EB curing (cross-linking)	For this subcategory the central point is to check if feasibility tests have been performed; if yes, the data test should be provided, specifying the equipment used for the tests

mechanical perforation	For this subcategory the central point is to check if feasibility tests have been performed; if yes, the data test should be provided, specifying the equipment used for the tests, and the minimum perforation resistance
laser perforation	For this subcategory the central point is to check if feasibility tests have been performed; if yes, the data test should be provided, specifying the equipment used for the tests, the possible laser shapes, and the mini and maxi tear resistance
slitting	For this subcategory the central point is to check if feasibility tests have been performed; if yes, the data test should be provided, specifying the equipment used for the tests, and the mini and maxi possible width
Orientation (mono or bi)	For this subcategory the central point is to check if feasibility tests have been performed; if yes, the data test should be provided, specifying the equipment used for the tests, the mini/maxi orientation ratio machine direction, mini / maxi orientation ratio transversal direction, and the mini/maxi possible thickness
Labeling	For this subcategory the central point is to check if feasibility tests have been performed; if yes, the data test should be provided, specifying the equipment used for the tests

3. Food product end-user specifications

3.1 Categories of food products related to the selection of packaging

This step of the specification work is very complex to establish as reference lists already established to classify the food products are rather based on the representation of the food industry, and not from the perspective of a classification of technical specifications. After debates in the consortium, the choice is to start on the basis of the classification of food products proposed in packaging food contact regulation (R10-2011), where food categories and subcategories are defined on the basis of food packaging interactions. The following categories were then defined:

- Beverages
- Cereals, cereal products, pastry, biscuits, cakes, and other bakers’ wares
- Chocolate, sugar and products thereof
- Confectionery products
- Fruit, vegetables, and products thereof
- Fats and oils
- Animal products and eggs
- Milk products
- Miscellaneous products.

3.2 Subcategories of food products

Subcategories proposed in R10-2011 are directly based on the ability of food to establish undesirable interactions with packaging, completed by the conditions of transformation (e.g. type of thermal treatment).

Table 3: Subcategories related to food products

Food product	Subcategory
Beverages	Non-alcoholic beverages or alcoholic beverages of an alcoholic strength lower than or equal to 6 % vol.:
	Alcoholic beverages of an alcoholic strength of between 6 %vol and 20 %.
	Alcoholic beverages of an alcoholic strength above 20 % and all cream liquors
	Miscellaneous: undenatured ethyl alcohol
Cereals, cereal products, pastry, biscuits, cakes, and other bakers’ wares	Starches
	Cereals, unprocessed, puffed, in flakes (including popcorn, corn flakes and the like)
	Cereal flour and meal
	Dry pasta e.g. macaroni, spaghetti, and similar products and fresh pasta
	Pastry, biscuits, cakes, bread, and other bakers’ wares, dry:
	Pastry, cakes, bread, dough and other bakers’ wares, fresh:
Chocolate, sugar and products thereof	
Confectionery products	Chocolate, chocolate-coated products, substitutes and products coated with substitutes
	Confectionery products:
	Sugar and sugar products

Fruit, vegetables, and products thereof	Whole fruit, fresh or chilled, unpeeled
	Processed fruit dried
	Processed fruits with no thermal treatment
	Processed fruits pasteurized
	Processed fruits appertized
	Nuts (peanuts, chestnuts, almonds, hazelnuts, walnuts, pine kernels, and others), selled dried and or roasted
	Nuts (peanuts, chestnuts, almonds, hazelnuts, walnuts, pine kernels and others), inpaste or cream form
	Whole vegetables, fresh or chilled, unpeeled
	Processed vegetables Dried or dehydrated vegetables whole, sliced or in the form of flour or powder
	Processed Fresh vegetables, peeled or cut no thermal treatment
	Processed Fresh vegetables, peeled or cut pasteurized
	Processed Fresh vegetables, peeled or cut appertized
	Preserved vegetables In an oily medium
	Preserved vegetables In an alcoholic medium
	Fats and oils
Margarine, butter and other fats and oils made from water emulsions in oil	
Animal products and eggs	Fresh, chilled, processed, salted or smoked including fish eggs with no thermal process
	Fresh, chilled, processed, salted or smoked including fish eggs pasteurized
	Fresh, chilled, processed, salted or smoked including fish eggs appertised
	Preserved fish In an oily medium, appertized
	Crustaceans and mollusks (including oysters, mussels, snails) Fresh within the shell
	Crustaceans and mollusks (including oysters, mussels, snails) Shell removed, processed, preserved or cooked with the shell pasteurized
	Crustaceans and mollusks (including oysters, mussels, snails) Shell removed, processed, preserved or cooked with the shell appertized
	Meat of all zoological species (including poultry and game): Fresh, chilled, salted, smoked
	Meat of all zoological species (including poultry and game) Processed meat products (such as ham, salami, bacon, sausages, and other) or in the form of paste, creams
	Meat of all zoological species (including poultry and game): Marinated meat products in an oily medium
	appertized meat, In a fatty or oily medium
	pasteurized meat In a fatty or oily medium
	appertized meat In an aqueous medium
	pasteurized meat In an aqueous medium
	Whole eggs, egg yolk, egg white powered
	Whole eggs, egg yolk, egg white dried
	Whole eggs, egg yolk, egg white frozen
	Whole eggs, egg yolk, egg white
	Whole eggs, egg yolk, egg white, liquid
	Whole eggs, egg yolk, egg white cooked

Milk products	Milk and milk-based drinks whole, partly dried and skimmed or partly skimmed, no thermal treatment
	Milk and milk-based drinks whole, partly dried and skimmed or partly skimmed, pasteurized
	Milk and milk-based drinks whole, partly dried and skimmed or partly skimmed, UHT
	Milk powder including infant formula (based on whole milk powder)
	Fermented milk such as yogurt, buttermilk, and similar products
	Cream and sour cream no thermal treatment
	Cream and sour cream no thermal treatment
	Cream and sour cream pasteurized
	Cream and sour cream UHT
	Cheeses Whole, with not edible rind
	Cheeses Natural cheese without rind or with edible rind (gouda, camembert, and the like) and melting cheese
	Cheeses Processed cheese (soft cheese, cottage cheese and similar)
	Cheeses Preserved cheese in an oily medium
	Cheeses : preserved cheese In an aqueous medium (feta, mozzarella, and similar)
Miscellaneous products	Vinegar
	Fried or roasted foods: Fried potatoes, fritters and the like
	Fried or roasted foods: Of animal origin
	Preparations for soups, broths, sauces, in liquid, solid or powder form (extracts, concentrates); homogenized composite food preparations, prepared dishes including yeast and raising agents
	Preparations for soups, broths, sauces, in liquid, solid or powder form (extracts, concentrates); homogenized composite food preparations, prepared dishes including yeast and raising agents, powdered or dried
	Preparations for soups, broths, sauces, in liquid, solid or powder form (extracts, concentrates); homogenized composite food preparations, prepared dishes including yeast and raising agents
	Sauces: With aqueous character
	Sauces: With fatty character e.g. mayonnaise, sauces derived from mayonnaise, salad creams and other oil/water mixtures e.g. coconut-based sauces
	Mustard
	Sandwiches, Toasted bread pizza and the like containing any kind of foodstuff
	Ice-creams
	Frozen or deep-frozen foods
	Concentrated extracts of an alcoholic strength equal to or exceeding 6 % vol.
	Cocoa powder, including fat-reduced and highly fat reduced
	Cocoa paste
	Coffee, whether or not roasted, decaffeinated or soluble, coffee substitutes, granulated or powdered
	Aromatic herbs and other herbs such as chamomile, mallow, mint, tea, lime blossom, and others
	Spices and seasonings in the natural state such as cinnamon, cloves, powdered mustard, pepper, vanilla, saffron, salt and other
	Spices and seasoning in oily medium such as pesto, curry paste

3.3 Inventory of critical properties

In this part it was decided to focus on the main properties guide the choice of a packaging type; this is then not an exhaustive list of the needed properties for a given application; typical properties of interest for this part will be:

- Gas permeability in the intended conditions of use (process and storage)
- (for active absorber packaging): maximum acceptable cumulated water, oxygen, CO₂ intake or loss
- (for active emitter packaging): efficiency of food product stabilization established through an increase of shelf life compared to the efficiency of the reference non active packaging
- Barrier to light
- Composition of modified atmosphere, if relevant
- Control of leaks and micro leaks and sealing quality
- Adaptation to thermal food process (time/temperature mechanical resistance) or other physical or chemical treatments for packaging or food packaging sanitizing
- Absence of food packaging interactions leading to the loss of food packaging integrity.

4. Conditioning and end-user specifications

4.1 Categories of conditioning and end-user specifications

- a) For the conditioning operations, the majority of common specifications are based on a classification of packaging types, but some operation is common to several types of packaging. The first list proposed by CTCPA is the following :
- plastic rigid packaging
 - Trays made by the conditioner (generally soft trays) by thermoforming before conditioning operations
 - Thermo sealed rigid plastic packaging (trays or pot)
 - Plastic Bottles or pot with cap (clipped or screwed)
 - Plastic Bottles or pot, sealed, and with cap (clipped or screwed)
 - Plastic Bottles or pot, sealed
 - Crimped plastic package
 - plastic soft packaging
 - Soft pouches made by the conditioner before conditioning operations
 - Preformed pouches
 - blisters
 - Plastic blister
 - Board blister
 - metallic packaging
 - Crimped metal package
 - Metallic can, sealed
 - Aluminum tray
 - cardboard
 - Secondary flat cardboard packaging
 - Secondary corrugated cardboard packaging
 - Primary board packaging
 - glass
 - Glass bottle, cup, pot, with cap (clipped or screwed)
 - Glass bottle, cup, pot, sealed
 - others
 - Packaging systems with pumps
 - Packaging systems with valves
 - Glass pot with thick to ring.
- b) The issue is that the classification by packaging types not allows to express all types of specifications related to the conditioning; it was then decided to propose other categories of specifications, reflecting specific process:
- Chemical sanitizing pretreatments of packaging
 - Physical sanitizing pretreatments of packaging.

4.2 Inventory of critical properties

Critical properties related to end-user specifications are listed in Table 4:

Table 4: Critical properties of end-user specifications

Critical property	Applicable to
Destacking	Trays, cups
Sealing ability	Soft packaging, sealed trays and cups
Mechanical resistance	Films
Electrostatic properties (for machinability)	Films
Electrostatic properties (dust catching)	All packaging

Important remark concerning both the specifications of end-users/conditioning and end-users/food preservation:

As the combination of product/packaging type/conditioning options leads to an extremely wide number of possibilities, it is not possible to present the specification through tables. It was then proposed to develop a software establish automatically these data, and allowing the link both from a use case to the specification needed but also from a set of properties to possible applications;

This should be built in the frame of the dissemination WP (to be validated by MyPack board).

5. Retailer specifications

5.1 Categories of retailer specifications

This task was led by Lea Nature; the following categories were defined:

- adaptation to palletization: sure this category of specifications is typically poorly considered in a packaging innovation process, which focuses generally on “more important” (considered as) technological steps;
- traceability and inviolability: this aspect becomes more and more important to ensure the quality of the retailing step. Technologies are developed on “classical” packaging; new packaging technologies have to be compatible with existing traceability and inviolability systems; if not adapted solution has to be developed;
- adaptation to fill the store shelves: this step is critical for retailers / economic (negative) impacts (of un-adapted packaging);
- adaptation to supermarket checkout;
- adaptation to drives (easy to buy from a photo);
- adaptation to store shelves: again this aspect can be considered as “non-technical” by packaging developers; nevertheless this set of specifications contains critical aspects such as the packaging geometry;
- specialized distribution networks: low scale retailers have specifications related to the reception of a blend of references in the same secondary packaging.

5.2 Subcategories of retailer specifications

It was not necessary to define subcategories.

5.3 Inventory of critical properties

The critical properties were converted into a simple questionnaire:

Table 5: Critical properties of retailer specifications

Technological step or property category	Critical property
adaptation to palettization	products sold in heterogeneous pallets? optimized for euro pallet 80 120? the need for intercalation sheets? need to stretch palletizing film? non-self-supporting product (or secondary packed product)? self-supporting product (or secondary packed product)? resistance to vibrations tested?
traceability and inviolability	gen code on uvc ? gen code on secondary product? gen code on pallet? presence of an inviolability system?
adaptation to fill the store shelves	easy open of overpack (no need of cutter)? minimized the quantity of board waste? secondary packaging is adapted to counter display / easier facing?
adaptation to supermarket checkout	verification of article weight during the checkout?

	good visibility of gencode ?
adaptation to drives (easy to buy from a photo)	adapted quality of photos? clear dimensions of packaged product? clear weight? clear designation of a product?
adaptation to store shelves	adapted to 400 mm deep? (e.g. 2X20 cm or 1X40 or 3X 13 cm) adapted facing / graphical charter? double facing? (for little shops) adaptation of quantities in secondary packs to the product shelflife? resistance to falling tested?
specialized distribution networks	packaging adapted? (e.g. easy unpacking of secondary packaging)
organic product	packaging is in good consistency with environmental and ethic requirements? fulfills negative lists of packaging materials (e.g. PVC ?)

Remark: additional critical properties were defined for palletized products, including the resistance to vertical compression

6. Regulations and end life specifications

The specific task objective is to set up regulatory guidelines concerning already regulated issues.

6.1 Categories of regulations and end life specifications

The following categories were identified: “food contact”, “environment”, “information of consumers (INCO regulation)”, “nano packaging regulations” and “smart packaging regulations”.

6.2 Subcategories of regulations and end life specifications

For the further process, we split up in smaller groups regarding the different categories.

6.2.1 Food contact properties

The following checklist was proposed as a simplified summary of the requirements of food contact properties:

Table 6: Summary of requirements for food contact properties

Food contact	Questions
	intended food applications defined (food type(s), pH, fat content..)?
	Intended conditions of use defined (time-temperature technological steps)
	Material composition known? (type of polymer and substances submitted to restriction)
	Formulation optimized to minimize migration: experimental or modeling tests performed?
	(if a step of material transformation is not classical if any composition of the material is not classical) : Study of non intended added substances was performed?
	(if the formulation contains substances submitted to LMS) and (if you intend to evaluate specific migration by modeling): material formulation, identity, and geometry of layer are known and modeling tests were performed for each intended condition of use?
	(if the formulation contains substances submitted to LMS) and (if you intend to evaluate specific migration by experimental tests: specific migration tests were performed for each intended conditions of use?
	overall migration tests were performed for each intended conditions of use?
	Organoleptic inertia tests were performed for each intended conditions of use? (especially for paperboard packaging or for substances or impurities submitted to absence or limit concentrations in the material) : do you fulfill the requirements (absence or limit concentrations) of material composition?

As an additional checklist the following specification was added; these specifications are not obligatory :

Did you explore strategies to limit the presence or the migration of potential endocrine disruptors, nanofillers, inks, mineral oils?

6.2.2 Environmental specifications

The issue of environmental legislation is the diversity of requirements and opportunities as a function of the considered country or region.

It was then decided to make different versions of the following questions in 9 countries in Europe. The same information for more EU member states shall be added during the further project.

Table 7: Questions for environmental specifications

End of life	Questions	Remarks
Material composition	fulfills requirements of material composition?	if yes precise with which national collection system it is incompatible
National collection system	collected?	
Industrial sorting	designed/adapted to NIR- separator? designed/adapted to Air separator? designed/adapted to Color sorting (PET)?	
Material recycling	designed/adapted to Food contact recycling? designed / adapted to Textile recycling (?) designed/adapted to Grinding, washing, density separation (swim-sink), drying, extrusion?	
Combustion	can be used as RDF?	if yes precise the labels/regulations which are filled
Composting	compostable? existing infrastructure in the commercialization zone of the product?	if yes precise the labels/regulations which are filled
Biodegradability	designed adapted to Home-composting?	if yes precise conditions and end products demonstrated
Chemical recycling	designed/adapted to chemical recycling?	

A general overview of the regulations for biodegradable and compostable plastics packaging and bioplastics packaging, in general, is provided below:

Table 8: Summary of regulations for bioplastics packaging in Belgium, Germany, and the Netherlands

Critical property	Belgium	Germany	The Netherlands
National packaging legislation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Samenwerkingsakkoord van 04112008 - Decret of Wallonia on plastic bags of 06072017 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Packaging law from 05072017 - Biowaste Ordinance of 21091998 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overeenkomst afvalbeheersbijdrage of 28122017 - Packaging Decree of 18122015
material composition	Not allowed in biowaste	Not allowed in biowaste	Not allowed in biowaste
National collection system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Plastics bottles and flasks in blue bag from households - FostPlus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Plastics/light packaging in yellow bag from households - 9 companies in competition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Plastics/light packaging from households or containers - Afvalfonds Verpakkingen (Packaging Waste

			Fund) - Costs of packaging of biodegradable plastics are less
Industrial sorting	Not for bioplastics	Not for bioplastics	Not for bioplastics
Material recycling	Not for bioplastics	Not for bioplastics	Not for bioplastics
Combustion	Yes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - with residual waste or - sorted out with mixed plastics as RDF - sorted out from compostable waste 	Yes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - with residual waste or - sorted out with mixed plastics as RDF - sorted out from compostable waste 	Yes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - with residual waste or - sorted out with mixed plastics as RDF - sorted out from compostable waste
Composting	Not for bioplastics <u>packaging</u>	Not for bioplastics <u>packaging, but for biodegradable plastic waste that is certified acc. EN 13432 and not packaging</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Biowaste bags, that are certified acc. EN 13432 - Biological treatment is considered as recycling
Biodegradability and compostability	Possible, if certified acc. EN 13432	Possible, if certified acc. EN 13432	Possible, if certified acc. EN 13432
Chemical recycling	No information yet	No information yet	No information yet

Table 9: Summary of regulations for biodegradable and compostable plastics packaging in France, Italy, and Spain

Critical property	France	Italy	Spain
National packaging legislation	French Environmental Code (Articles R.543-42 and following)	Refer to EU Directive DLgs 152/2006: Environmental regulation for waste DLgs 205/2010: sorting waste regulation D.M. 18 March 2013: bags for organic waste L 123/2017: technical requirements for plastic bags, biodegradable/compostable	R- Refere to EU Directive - Ley 22/2011, de 28 de julio, de residuos y suelos contaminados.
material composition	Fruit and Vegetable bags "Home compostable"	If EN 13432 certified allowed in biowaste. EN 16640:2017 for minimum percentage of bio raw material. No specification for not biodegradable/compostable bioplastic and additives.	
National collection system	Yes, France is planning to introduce a penalty system in 2019 to increase the cost of	Yes, national consortium (CONAI) Plastics/light packaging in yellow bags from	Yes, National Consortium for plastic packaging: ECOEMBES

	consumer goods using non-recycled plastic packaging.	households or yellow containers. Biodegradable and compostable plastic (EN 13432) in bio-waste.	
Industrial sorting		Yes, for plastics	Yes
Material recycling		Only for plastic packaging (14 %); biodegradable and compostable materials can be treated in composting plants	69,7% of plastic containers recycled (Ecoembes)
Combustion	-	Yes - with residual waste or - sorted out with mixed plastics as RDF - sorted out from compostable waste	-
Composting		Biowaste bags, that are certified acc. EN 13432 Food compostable bags and foodservice tableware (voluntary scheme)	
Biodegradability and compostability		Possible, if certified acc. EN 13432	
Chemical recycling		Not known	

Table 10: Summary of regulations for bioplastics packaging in Austria, Sweden, Denmark

Critical property	Austria	Sweden	Denmark
National packaging legislation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Packaging Ordinance from 22072014 - Biowaste Ordinance of 01011995 - Compost Ordinance of 01092001 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Swedish Regulations on Producer Responsibility for Packaging (2014: 1073) of 2014/2016 - Chapter 15 of the Swedish environmental code - Deposit Ordinance SFS 2005:220 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Danish Environmental Protection Act (Consolidation Act no. 879 of 26 June 2010) - Tax system for packaging waste
material composition	If certified allowed in biowaste	Biodegradable and compostable packaging allowed in biowaste	If EN 13432 certified allowed in biowaste
National collection system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Either plastics/light packaging in yellow bag from households <u>or</u> plastics bottles/ metal packaging from households or containers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - FTI: collection and recycling of packaging and newspaper - Returpack: Deposit plastic bottles - Glas: Svensk GlasÅtervinning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dansk return system: deposit and return system for bottles and cans - Packaging Waste Fund

	- 6 companies in competition		
Industrial sorting	Not for bioplastics	Not for bioplastics	Not for bioplastics
Material recycling	Not for bioplastics	Not for bioplastics	Not for bioplastics
Combustion	Yes - with residual waste or - sorted out with mixed plastics as RDF	Yes - with residual waste or - sorted out with mixed plastics as RDF	Yes - with residual waste
Composting	Certified biodegradable and compostable plastics	- Biowaste bags, that are certified acc. EN 13432 - Biological treatment is considered as recycling – bioplastics sorted out	- Biowaste bags from municipalities - Biological treatment is considered as recycling
Biodegradability and compostability	Possible, if certified	Possible, if certified acc. EN 13432 or national standard	
Chemical recycling	No information yet	No information yet	No information yet

Remark: a deeper work will be done on the various definitions of “home compostable” and “compostable”, as a function of regulations and private labels.

Table 11: Overview of regulative and other barriers to bioplastics

Country	Legislative position	Financial incentive	Infrastructure for composting / fermentation	Cycle of composting
Austria	Indifferent	No	Well developed	6 weeks – 4 months
Belgium	Indifferent	No	Well developed	
Denmark	Indifferent	No	In development	
France	Positive	No	In development	3 – 6 months
Germany	Negative / indifferent	No	Well developed	3 – max. 15 weeks
Italy	Positive	No	Well developed	3 months
Spain	Indifferent	No	In development	
Sweden	Indifferent	No	Well developed	2 – 3 months
The Netherlands	Indifferent	No	Well developed	2 – 6 weeks

For the property category “environment” rather fast two main issues – subcategories - have been identified in the further discussions of the group, which are “end-of-life” and “European labels concerning biodegradability”.

Table 12: Subcategories identified for category "Environment"

Categories	Subcategories	Comments
Environment	End-of-life	End-of-life for packaging holds many regulations since each member of the EU has passed own regulations in accordance with the European Directive on packaging and packaging waste. The differences of these regulations are multifarious and lead therefore to very different ways how it is dealt with packaging and bioplastic packaging in each country. As a result, there has to be set up a version of the following critical properties "national packaging legislation", "cost of end-of-life" and "legally privileged markets for bioplastics" for each country. Since this is very much work to do, it was decided to collect the data in a first step for the member states Belgium, Germany, France, Italy, Spain, and the Netherlands.
	European labels concerning biodegradability	

6.3 Inventory of critical properties

Table 13: Critical properties for regulations and end life specifications

Subcategories	Comments on the critical properties selected
End-of-life	<p><u>National packaging legislation:</u> The further critical properties are the various possibilities of how it can be dealt with packaging – collection systems, industrial sorting, mechanical or chemical recycling, composting, biodegradability, combustion. These critical properties are examined until the final aggregate, i. e. NIR- or air-separator, composting features.</p> <p><u>Cost of end-of-life:</u> The further critical properties found here are landfill, combustion, composting, recycling, biodegradability</p> <p><u>Legally privileged markets for bioplastics:</u> As some member states grant privileges for biodegradable packaging, these privileges – kinds of privileges - are a further critical point that has to be mentioned and is different in each country.</p>
European labels concerning biodegradability	

6.4 Legislation on packaging waste

At EU level the main legislation on packaging waste is the Directive 94/62/EC on packaging and packaging waste and the Directive (EU) 2018/852 amending Directive 94/62/EC on packaging and packaging waste. The aim of the Directive is to prevent the production of plastic waste

6.4.1 What is the aim of the directive?

Directive 94/62/EC sets out the EU's rules on managing packaging and packaging waste.

Directive (EU) 2018/852 amends Directive 94/62/EC and contains updated measures designed to:

- prevent the production of packaging waste, and
- promote the reuse, recycling and other forms of recovering of packaging waste, instead of its final disposal, thus contributing to the transition towards a circular economy*.

Directive 94/62/EC aims to contribute to:

- improving the quality of the environment;
- protecting human health;
- protecting resources;
- ensure the functioning of the internal market and restrictions on competition within the EU.

6.4.2 Key points

Scope

The directive as amended covers all packaging placed on the European market and all packaging waste, whether it is used or released at industrial, commercial, office, shop, service, household or any other level, regardless of the material used.

Measures

EU countries must take measures, such as national programs, incentives through extended producer responsibility schemes and other economic instruments, to prevent the generation of packaging waste and to minimize the environmental impact of packaging.

EU countries should encourage the increase in the share of reusable packaging* put on the market and of systems to reuse packaging without compromising food safety. This may include:

- deposit-return schemes
- targets
- economic incentives
- minimum percentages of reusable packaging placed on the market for each type of packaging, etc.

EU countries must also take the necessary measures to meet certain recycling targets which vary depending on packaging material and for this purpose apply the new calculation rules.

Targets

By 31 December 2025, at least 65% by weight of all packaging must be recycled. The recycling targets for each material are:

- 50% of plastic
- 25% of wood
- 70% of ferrous metals
- 50% of aluminum
- 70% of glass, and
- 75% of paper and cardboard.

By 31 December 2030, at least 70% of packaging must be recycled. This includes:

- 55% of plastic
- 30% of wood
- 80% of ferrous metals
- 60% of aluminum
- 75% of glass and
- 85% of paper and cardboard.

Essential requirements

EU countries must ensure that the packaging placed on the market meets the essential requirements contained in Annex II of the directive:

- to limit the weight and volume of packaging to a minimum in order to meet the required level of safety, hygiene and acceptability for consumers;
- to reduce the content of hazardous substances and materials in the packaging material and its components;
- to design reusable or recoverable packaging.

Biodegradable packaging: oxo-degradable* plastic packaging must not be considered as biodegradable.

The European Commission is currently examining how to reinforce the essential requirements with the view to improving packaging design for reuse and promoting high-quality recycling, as well as strengthening the enforcement of the essential requirements.

Packaging recovery systems

EU countries should ensure that systems are set up to provide for the return and/or collection of used packaging and/or packaging waste, as well as the reuse or recovery including recycling of the packaging and/or packaging waste collected.

Producer responsibility

By 2025, EU countries should ensure that producer responsibility schemes* are established for all packaging. Producer responsibility schemes provide for the return and/or collection of used packaging and/or packaging waste and its channeling to the most appropriate waste management option, as well as for reuse or recycling of the collected packaging and packaging waste. These schemes will need to comply with some minimum requirements established under the Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC). The schemes should help

incentivize packaging that is designed, produced and commercialized in a way that allows its reuse or recovery and that has minimal impact on the environment.

From when does the directive apply?

Directive 94/62/EC has applied since 31 December 1994 and had to become law in the EU countries by 30 June 1996.

Directive (EU) 2018/852 has applied since 4 July 2018 and had to become law in the EU countries by 5 July 2020.

Background

For more information, see:

Packaging and packaging waste (European Commission).

*Key terms

Circular economy: a circular economy minimizes resource input, waste, emissions, and energy leakage. It can be achieved through long-lasting design, maintenance, repair, reuse, and recycling. It contrasts with a linear economy that extracts resources, uses them, then throws them away.

Reusable packaging: packaging which has been conceived, designed and marketed to carry out multiple trips in its lifetime by being refilled or reused for the same purpose for which it was conceived.

Oxo-degradable: oxo-degradable packaging is plastic packaging with additives that cause it to break down into microscopic particles. It can contribute to the presence of microplastics in the environment.

Producer responsibility scheme: a system set up by a producer to ensure that they bear some of the responsibility of reducing some of the environmental impacts of the manufacture, placing on the market and disposal of their products.

6.5 Regulations related to plastic materials

In this section, only regulations relating to plastic materials intended for contact with foodstuffs are taken into account. It aims to lay the necessary foundations allowing to answer the regulatory obstacles related to the manufacture of different materials that are covered or that are not covered by a specific regulation under the MYPACK project. Strategic solutions are proposed to meet the various obstacles.

In this context, the requirements of the various following regulations concerned by the MYPACK project are summarized in this document:

- **Regulation EC No. 1935/2004** on materials and articles intended to come into contact with food
- **Regulation EU No. 10/2011** on plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with food
- **Regulation EC No. 282/2008** on recycled plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with foods
- **Regulation EC No. 450/2009** on active and intelligent materials and articles intended to come into contact with food
- **Regulation EC No. 2023/2006** on good manufacturing practice for materials and articles intended to come into contact with food
- Modeling guide

6.5.1 Regulation EC No. 1935/2004

Regulation EC No. 1935/2004 of the European Union lays down the regulatory framework and the general requirements applicable to all materials intended for contact with foodstuffs. Article 3 of that regulation defines the inertia principle as a requirement for all materials and articles which must not yield to foodstuffs quantities of constituents which:

- Present a danger to human health;
- Unacceptably altering the composition of foods (except in the case of active packaging if food additive);
- Modify the organoleptic properties of foodstuffs (except in the case of active packaging if food additive).

These three requirements apply to substances and materials that will be used or manufactured as part of the MYPACK project.

This regulation also requires that materials intended to come into contact with food be manufactured using good practices. The provisions of good manufacturing practices are defined in the regulation EC No. 2023/2006 and correspond to the implementation of a quality management system or hygiene.

The scope of the framework regulation includes the list of groups of materials and processes that may be subject to specific measures, i.e. criteria defining the contact with food of these materials groups and processes. Specific measures can be defined by a group of materials or objects in regulations or directives; this is currently the case for plastics including those resulting from recycling processes, ceramics, regenerated cellulose film, materials and objects active and/or intelligent and partially for rubbers and epoxy coatings. However, there is no specific measure, described in a specific European text, for each material falling within the scope of the Regulation. In addition, the European regulation provides that in the absence of a harmonized provision for one type of material, the national provisions of each member state apply (Article 6), while respecting the principle of recognition described in regulation (EC) n° 764/2008.

Article 16 of framework Regulation (EC) No. 1935/2004 requires different supply chain operators to provide written declarations of conformity to their customers for the different materials subject to regulatory requirements on the basis of support documentation and with two objectives:

- Confirm that the delivered products comply with the regulatory requirements;
- Communicate to customers the information needed to establish or verify the compliance of finished products with the regulations under normal and reasonably foreseeable conditions of use.

The European Commission is responsible for all authorizations of substances in the form of specific measures and EFSA (European Food Safety Authority) investigates the files for any new substance and makes scientific opinions within 6 months renewable once.

6.5.2 General requirements for plastic materials – Regulation (EU) No. 10/2011 and Regulation (EC) No. 282/2008

Plastic materials fall within the scope of Regulation (EU) No. 10/2011. The main requirements for these materials are in compliance with the EU list for the formulation of these materials and compliance with overall and specific migration thresholds.

Since its publication on January 15, 2011, and its entry into force on 01/05/2011, the regulation (EU) No. 10/2011 has been revised 10 times. Three guides (Guide JRC Technical Reports, 2015; European Commission, 2013, 2014;) for the implementation of this regulation were published and updated between 2009 and 2015: one on the modelling of substance migration, another on the written declaration of conformity and adequate information in the plastics supply chain and the latter gives general guidance on the application of the regulation.

More fully, according to Regulation (EU) No. 10/2011, plastics must meet the following requirements:

- Be made using the following substances:
 - Monomers, starting substances, macromolecules obtained by microbial fermentation, additives which appear in the European Union list and for certain substances, respecting the maximum permitted quantities in materials (Q_m in mg/kg of material);
 - Substances not listed in the European Union list but covered by derogations (polymeric additives, prepolymers, acid salts, alcohols and phenols of aluminium, ammonium, barium, calcium, cobalt, copper, iron, lithium, magnesium, manganese, potassium, sodium and zinc, mixtures of substances, substance of the EU provisional list);
 - Substances not listed in the European Union list but evaluated under the responsibility of the operators according to the scientific principles of internationally recognized risk assessment (dyestuffs, solvents, unintentionally added substances, reaction and degradation products).
- Do not migrate to foods (or their simulants) beyond the following thresholds, under normal and foreseeable conditions of use of finished articles:
 - Overall Migration Limit (adult feeding $OML \leq 10 \text{ mg} / \text{dm}^2$ and OML infant feeding $\leq 60 \text{ mg} / \text{kg}$ food) for non-volatile substances;
 - Specific Migration Limits (SML in mg/kg) for all substances subject to restrictions of use in the EU list;
 - Migration limits for non-listed substances based on the results of the risk assessment or thresholds authorized at the national level.

The compliance demonstration of plastic materials is the most often based on migration testing to assess the specific migration limit of authorized substances. As migration testing is complex, costly and time-consuming, the regulation (EU) No. 10/2011 allows also the compliance demonstration of these materials by calculations, including modeling by applying generally recognized diffusion models based on scientific evidence in order to overestimate the real migration. Modeling can be also used upstream of the design of a new material. The aim is to modulate the amount of substances that will be migrated in the food according to the kind of food that will be used.

Articles 15 and 16 and Annex IV to Regulation (EU) No. 10/2011 specify the specific requirements for plastics with regard to the written declaration of conformity and the supporting documentation. Only the written declaration of conformity is required for the exchange of information between operators.

In parallel, the provisions of Regulation (EC) n° 282/2008 (amended by Regulation (EU) 2015/1906 of October 22, 2015) concerning plastic recycling processes have been put in place and opinions have been delivered by the EFSA to authorize processes and production sites for recycled plastics intended for contact with food. Recycled plastic materials and articles shall only be placed on the market if they contain recycled plastic obtained only from a recycling process, authorized in accordance with this Regulation.

This Regulation shall apply to the plastic materials and articles and parts thereof intended to come into contact with foodstuffs. It applies to all scraps and Offcuts from the production of plastic intended in food contact materials, but which has not been in contact with food except in the case:

- Waste plastics decomposed into monomers and oligomers by chemical depolymerization
- Recycled plastics on-site and uncontaminated (regrind)
- Plastics used behind a functional barrier.

6.5.3 Regulation (EC) No.450/2009 on active and intelligent material in contact with food

Active and intelligent materials and articles fall within the scope of regulation (EC) No. 1935/2004 concerning materials and articles intended for food contact. These materials are the subject of a specific regulation at the level of the European Union which is Commission Regulation (EC) No. 450/2009 of 29 May 2009.

In accordance with article 5 of Regulation (EC) n° 1935/2004, the regulation (EC) n° 450/2009 defines the specific requirements for active and intelligent materials and packaging. Article 4 of Regulation (EC) No. 1935/2004 had already described provisions to be complied with, pending the implementation of additional requirements. These provisions were as follows:

- The authorization of active ingredients provided that they are authorized as food ingredients;
- The action of active or intelligent components on foods that must not mislead consumers;
- The labeling that should alert the non-edibility and action of active and intelligent components on food.

The new provisions concern among other things:

- The rules for authorizing substances that can be used in active or intelligent materials;
- The migration of active compounds not accounted for in the overall migration results;
- The release of active compounds authorized up to the thresholds allowed in food;
- The provisions to be respected concerning labeling;
- The written declaration of compliance and the documentation to be kept by the operators.

Following the entry into force of Regulation (EC) No. 450/2009, in August 2009, EFSA has published on its website guidelines (EFSA, 2009) on "active" or "intelligent" substances contained in food contact materials. These guidelines are intended for industrials and specify how to submit evaluation applications for the safety of these substances. These guidelines list the criteria that will be taken into account by EFSA when assessing the safety of these substances, for example, their toxicological properties and the extent to which these substances, or their degradation products, can be transferred to food. The document also defines the data types that EFSA needs to conduct its assessments, including the physical or chemical characteristics of the substances involved as well as their manufacturing process and intended uses.

6.5.4 Methodology proposed to answer regulatory requirements under the Mypack project

Regulatory barriers must be considered since the beginning of the conception of new packaging in the framework of MYPACK project. This part consists of proposing a methodological approach to respond to the

regulatory obstacles related to the materials that will be produced in the project. Indeed, modeling the migration helps demonstrate the conformity of plastic packaging materials with regard to SMLs. In a more general context, modeling the contamination can be coupled with consumer data and/or household and industrial practices to assess chronic consumer exposure to one or several substances. The following table sums up the different technological factors affecting the contamination of food. In the case of migration through contact, the level of contamination depends on the contact area, the quality of the contact between the packaging and the food and the contact time.

Table 14: Main technological factors affecting food contamination

Evolution of factor	Consequence of contamination	Examples
↗Concentration of contaminant in packaging before being packaged	↗	Production incident
↗Contact time	↗	Use by date, best before date
↗Contact area	↗	Rather wide joint Adhesive seal
↗Packing temperature	↗	Hot filling
↗Temperature of conservation	↗	Frozen, refrigerated, room temperature
↗ Thermal stabilization treatment	↗	Pasteurization, sterilization of packaged food
↗Heating up temperature/cooking with packaging	↗	Bain-marie, microwave
Shaping of material	variable	Coextrusion/thermoforming of multilayers, blow molding
↘Size of contaminant	↗	Plasticizer
↗Chemical affinity of contaminant for food product	↗	Fatty food (hydrophobic)
State of polymer	↗↗ above Tg	Hot filling uncontrolled
↗Chemical affinity of food product for polymer	↗	Sorption of food substances into packaging
↗Hydrostatic pressure	↘	Pascalization

Source: Hamaide et al., 2014

In this context, before any development of materials in this project, it is essential to proceed with these 5 steps specified in the FMECAengine approach (Vitrac et al, 2017; Nguyen et al., n.d):

- Identify the substances that can migrate and the properties associated with these substances (CAS number, chemical identity, molecule size, volatility, affinity for fatty or aqueous foods ...);
- For each substance present in the formulation of packaging materials, the existence of a health risk assessment (regulatory, technical and toxicological information) for use in food contact materials should be sought. In other words, the restrictions of use must be identified for each one of them (SML, Qm, purity criteria, conditions of employment,) ;
- Decomposition of the packaging into components (body, cap, lid, ...) and materials;
- Decomposition of the manufacture steps, storage and use of each element/component (with or without food);

- List any contamination mechanisms identified or reasonably imaginable.

Based on these 5 steps, it is relatively easy to identify a small number of priority situations for which a risk analysis is required. This approach applies equally to packaging already on the market, to new packaging, or to any modification of the design or end use (new contact, microwave reheating, etc.). However, priorities must be defined first by regulatory requirements and then by incorporating the elements of a voluntary approach.

The tools used to evaluate packaging contamination of food are highly developed (specific analyzes, deformation by NMR, migration modeling, etc.). In all cases, these strategies require the identification of critical components/steps and objective comparison of alternatives. The FMECAEngine approach detailed above allows exploring in a few minutes the potentialities of the chosen technical choices. It is also possible to evaluate the transfer properties (partition and diffusion coefficients) for each of the substances in order to obtain a more realistic assessment of the conformity of the materials.

6.6 Inventory tables to be completed by stakeholders

To proceed with the FMCAEngine approach under the MYPACK project, each project stakeholder is asked to complete the following tables with as much information as possible on their packaging systems (this table is also available in Excel format). This information will be used for the modeling and optimization of packaging systems from the design phase of the latter until their development.

Modeling Data Form

Part 1 : Material or article		
<u>1-Materials used to produce the article</u>		
Please specify the constituent layers of the material and specify the one in contact with the food,		Polymer (PE, PP, etc...)
	Layer 1 (in direct contact)	
	Layer 2	
	Layer 3	
	Layer 4	
	Layer 5	
	Layer 6	

2- Geometric description of the article (shape and size)				
		Equation	Result	
<p>It is important for modeling the migration to know the size of the article (the contact surface, the thickness of each layer ...).</p> <p>Choose from this list the geometry corresponding to your article and fill in its dimensions. In the case where the geometry of the article is not listed, thank you to provide us directly the contact area (S) between the food and the material and volume (V) of the article !</p> <p>Please send us a specimen of the article, if possible !</p>	Rectangular	$a*b*c$ (cm)		
	Cube	a (cm)		
	Cylinder	diameter (cm)		
		Height (cm)		
	Spherical	diameter (cm)		
	Cone	diameter (cm)		
		hauteur (cm)		
	Truncated cone	large diameter (cm)		
		Small diameter (cm)		
		Height (cm)		
Other	S (cm ²)			
	V (cm ³)			
The structure				
number of layers (n=)				
		Thickness e(μm)	Density D(g/cm3)	
Layer 1 (in direct contact)				
Layer 2				
Layer 3				
Layer 4				
Layer 5				
Layer 6				

3- List of substances (additives, monomers, etc.) consisting of the material				
		Substance	CAS No.	Concentration in the material (mg / kg) - Standard values can be specified
<p>Specify the monomers and additives used and their concentration in the manufacture of the material for the different layers.</p>	couche 1 (in direct contact)			
	couche 2			
	couche 3			
	couche 4			
	couche 5			
	couche 6			
	Substances present in the packaging but the relevant layer not determined			

Part 2 : Food products		
1- Food (s) in contact with the packaging		
Food families	Food used	
Aqueous foods only		
Acidic foods only		
Alcoholic foods only		
Fatty foods only		
Dry food		
All aqueous and acidic foods		
All alcoholic and aqueous foods		
All alcoholic and acidic foods		
All fatty and aqueous foods		
All fatty and acidic foods		
All fatty, alcoholic and aqueous foods		
All fatty, alcoholic and acidic foods		

The inertia of a material depends on the nature of the food in contact.
You can choose from the list the food family (s) concerned

Specific foods (by reference number according to EU Regulation No. 10/2011 or by the full description):
example> sausage

<u>2-Quantity of food product</u>			
Food volume (cm ³)			
Mass food (g)			
Part 3: Contact conditions (time and temperature)			
<p>The inertia of materials, which is the principle that all materials must meet, depends in particular on the contact time between the material and the food and the temperature.</p> <p>For example, a packaged food may experience different contact conditions at the following steps:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Conditioning operation (hot filling, pasteurization, sterilization, cooking, freezing,...) 2. Storage (cold, chilled, ambient) 3. Use by the consumer (thawing, reheating, cooking, ...) <p>Specify for each stage the time / temperature pair according to the actual use of the packaging or the article used to package the food.</p>	Step	Temperature (°C)	Time (sec)

Figure 2: Packaging systems inventory for modeling

7. Macroeconomic barriers

To find out macroeconomic barriers, it was agreed on the outlined methodology. During the work implementation, several meetings for the discussion of current progress and defining the next steps were held. The process was supported by calls and email communication with the targeted parties. As a conceptual framework, a gradual transition from the more general features to the specific ones was used.

Partners started with a review of the situation happening in the European market of bioplastics. A link to the global market was also needed to derive searchable conclusions. Since it is obvious that a current state of the market of interest differs within the EU, step-by-step, partners were moving to the analysis of the particular countries as the EU members.

A comprehensive overview lets define the main categories, which were used as a starting point in reaching a clear picture of the macroeconomic barriers. There are four categories: technology cost, market data, industry data, and circular economy - new plastics economy. Each category was subsequently divided into subcategories. These contain critical properties that are distinctive for each subcategory. The main target was to define and summarize as much data on critical properties as possible that can serve as a reliable basis for future actions.

7.1 Categories of macroeconomic barriers

The following categories of the macroeconomic barriers were identified:

- **Technology costs:** a primary and most influential barrier. High technology costs prevent an interested party from entering the market easily, restrict their abilities to be competitive, or eliminate the possibility to function in the industry. High setting up and operating investments may become a reason for a non-entry decision. High technology costs enhance the company's hesitation especially if the market situation is not stable. In addition, risk is bigger if it relates to the launch of a new production line, data on which is not yet available or not complete.
- **Market data:** The environment makes a decisive influence on the success of a company that operates in the industry. Every link in the production chain can hinder a product's path and, as a result, block reaching its final destination. If a monopoly in a related sector of the economy exists, some data is hidden or false, if the whole picture of the market's situation is not clear and some indicators are not considered, a company might face unexpected obstacles, which will throw the company out of a business.
- **Industry data:** successful business establishment and functioning do not depend only on the internal environment and strengths of the company. It is important to know that the industry is able to provide normal and beneficial conditions for business maintenance and development.
- **Circular economy - new plastics economy:** a circular economy is getting more attention throughout the world and seems to be a promising direction for the future. Support from the governments and third parties often play a critical role in business establishment and decision-making. In many cases, especially small companies, have a potential, but lack investments and/or legislative basis. A shortage

of attention to the R&D may lead to the omission of the opportunities to develop new ideas that might be crucial for improving economies and the life of humanity in general.

7.2 Subcategories of macroeconomic barriers

An all-embracing list of subcategories was defined by the working group and is provided in a table below:

Table 15: List of subcategories related to macroeconomic barriers

Categories	Subcategories	Comments
Technology costs	raw material supply	Those factors that directly determine the technology costs were combined into this category. The availability of the raw materials and land use for their production was analyzed. Every processing step for each technology has to be considered and well as possible end of life options
	land use	
	conversion	
	end of life	
Market data	polymer type	An overview of the market and production capacities of each related polymers as well as intermediate products was done. In addition, a situation on the market of competitive polymers was conducted
	market segment	
	competition	
Industry data	employment	The employment market of the industry has to be taken into account when introducing an innovative technology. An interested party has to be sure that there are enough other companies, which will directly influence business development. Also, an industry's turnover can serve as an indicator for further growth.
	companies	
	turnover	
Circular economy – new plastics economy	R&D	It is difficult for a company to survive and prosper, especially when it relates to innovations. Though, support programs and platforms that exist within the EU and on the local levels, were outlined.
	political support	

The next questions were set for each subcategory:

Table 16: Questions set for subcategories of macroeconomic barriers

Subcategories	Comments
raw material supply	Renewable feedstock? Yield? Harvested area? Scope of production? Producer prices?
land use	In a competition with food/feed? Agricultural area used? Efficiency of bioplastics yielding?
conversion	Processing steps? Intermediate products? Production capacities (including intermediate products)? Production costs constituents?

	Intermediate product prices?
end of life	End of life options? Secondary polymers? Compatibility with recycling stream?
polymer type	Production capacities (also forecast)? End product prices? Share in bioplastics production?
market segment	Sectors and applications? Privileged application markets?
competition	Fossil based competitors? Production costs? Fossil based plastics prices? Production capacities?
employment	Number of jobs? Number of employees? Direct gross employment?
companies	Number of companies (manufacturers, converters, recyclers)?
turnover	In the bioplastics industry? Compared to the plastics industry?
R&D	Technology readiness level? Market fully adapted?
political support	Investments framework? Investments in new bio-based capacities? Investment in the collection, sorting and recycling infrastructure? Legislative and regulatory frameworks? Public finances? European technology platforms? SME actions towards better resource efficiency?

7.3 Inventory of critical properties

Finding the critical properties seemed to be one of the most important steps, as the indicators that they contain, would have a huge impact on determining the best markets for the proposed technologies.

Table 17: Critical properties of subcategories related to macroeconomic barriers

Subcategories	Comments on the critical properties selected
raw material supply	All these subcategories were united to find out the total costs of production and possible sustainable solutions for a product's after-usage. The main point is to find the exact numbers of raw materials production that serve as an indication for potential production capacities of each offered packaging
land use	
conversion	
end of life	
polymer type	It is critical to identify a current scope of production of needed bioplastics (if these already exist), forecast indicators, and sectors of application as well as privileged markets. These subcategories also include data on competitors: market saturation, development level and prices of fossil-based and other competitive plastics
market segment	
competition	

employment	A central point is to analyze a number of jobs and employees generally in the plastics industry as well as in bioeconomy. Data on a number of manufacturers, converters, and recyclers is vital
companies	
turnover	
R&D	The critical points are investments in a bioplastics industry: new capacities, collection, sorting, recycling, public finances, etc. It is also important to find the existing European Funds and technology platforms, as well as regulations defining the legal conditions for the industry
political support	

7.3.1 Technology costs

In the research, besides analyzing in general market of bioplastics, high attention was put to two technologies – Mater-Bi and PEF, since macroeconomic barriers arise as one of the most influential factors impacting technologies’ development. Currency conversion was not done in this study in order to stick to the data from original sources.

Out of 13,4 billion ha of the global land surface, around 4,7 billion ha belong to agricultural areas (based on the data from European Bioplastics). Arable land consisting of 1,4 billion ha is used for production of feedstock for food and feed, material use, biofuels, and bioplastics (

Figure 3). Approximately 0.81 million ha (0.016 % of the global agricultural area) were used for growing feedstock for bioplastics in 2018. It is estimated that in 2023 only 1.02 million ha (that accounts for 0.020 %) of the global agricultural land will be used for bioplastics. It sounds to be a minor indicator. However, already such small numbers lead to the controversial discussions between scientists as well as representatives from the industries.

Figure 3. Land use estimation, 2018 (billion ha)

Even though a population is going to increase rapidly, projections still claim no competition regarding the land use is about to happen in the nearest future. Nevertheless, with a growing population, the demand for food crops will increase. This, in turn, after some time, might create conflicts with alternative feedstock for bioplastics. 9 billion people in 2030 will cause a 30 % increase in biomass production. Increasing meat consumption and higher living standards could lead to a 70 % increase in food demand. In such a situation,

the potential supply of food can be reduced due to the cultivation of non-food crops on the arable land. This could result in an artificial shortage. An outlook of the EU shows that until 2030 there will be a slow decline in the total agricultural land use (Figure 4); however, increasing yields will positively affect overall production growth. Also, this yields' increase will remain moderate, especially in the western Member States.

Figure 4. Development of the agricultural area in the EU

Figure 5 presents data on the harvested area and production capacities of the crops, which are the most important for the production of selected bioplastics – Mater-Bi (corn and artichokes) and PEF (chicory roots, corn, sugar cane, sugar beet, and wheat) (based on FAOSTAT).

Artichokes: area harvested in the EU, 2017

Artichokes: production in the EU, 2017 (%)

Chicory roots: area harvested in the EU, 2017

Chicory roots: production in the EU, 2017 (%)

Sugar cane: area harvested in the EU, 2017

Sugar cane: production in the EU, 2017 (%)

Sugar beet: area harveste in the EU, 2017

Sugar beet: production in the EU, 2017 (%)

Figure 5. Agricultural crops: area harvested, 2017 (ha) (left) and production in the EU, 2017 (%) (right)

Production of cereals is expected to grow during the next decade that is caused by a small growth in feed demand, temperate export promises and increasing importance of industrial uses. However, a stronger growth is restricted by a slower yield growth and limited potential for area extension. Total EU production of common wheat, barley, and corn as well as total domestic use are projected to increase in 2030 compared to 2018. In general, a market for main cereals at the EU level is characterized as saturated during the indicated period of time.

France, Germany, the UK, and Romania are the four biggest main kinds of cereal producing countries. It is expected that these countries will account for about 55 % of the EU production in 2030 remains one of the most important net exporters at the EU level. Poland, Spain, Hungary, and Italy will contribute about 23 % of EU supply, being, however, notable net importers in 2030.

In a period to 2030, demand for industrial use of main cereals is expected to grow. Between 2016-2018 and 2030, the use of cereals in the EU is projected to increase by 12 million tonnes. Industrial uses will cause almost 60 % of the increase (European Commission, 2018). Wheat shows the highest demand growth rates (1.9 % annually), followed by corn (1.6 %).

Not only the land availability but also the suitability of the land to particular crops may become a barrier. For example, usually raw sugar is sourced locally depending on the available in a region feedstock. However, it is obvious that not all feedstock can be effectively grown in every region. It should also be taken into account that non-food crops are less land efficient. For example, the highest yields of fermentable sugar per ha belong to sugar cane and sugar beet. Also, the production of sugars from lignocellulose is costlier. An additional obstacle in growing the lignocellulosic biomass associated with the prices of the enzymes and with their efficiency.

Table 18 presents the yield in tonnes per ha for selected countries. The data was taken from the statistical database of FAO. Thus, the Netherlands, Spain, Germany, and Greece had the highest yield of corn per ha in 2017 compared to other listed countries. The lowest yield was recorded for Belgium – only 1.4 tonnes/ha. Artichoke was grown most productively in Spain and Italy. Data for the production of artichoke in Belgium, Germany, and the Netherlands is not available. Belgium and the Netherlands, among indicated countries, are the leaders in chicory roots production (50.1 and 46.8 tonne/ha respectively). Sugar cane in Europe, according to FAO, is grown only in Spain and Portugal. Also, Portugal had 91.5 % of its production in 2017 with a yield of 89.0 tonnes/ha. However, the scope of production is limited to about 90 ha (2017); EU sugar

refineries depend totally on imported feedstock. Except for Italy and Greece, yield of sugar beet for the rest of the listed countries varied between 83.7-95.1 tonne/ha. The lowest indicators belong to Greece (2.6 tonne/ha) and Italy (3.8 tonnes/ha).

Table 18. Yield of selected crops, 2017 (tonne/ha)

Country	Feedstock					
	Corn	Artichoke	Chicory roots	Sugar cane	Sugar beet	Wheat
Belgium	1.4	n.a.	50.1	n.a.	95.1	8.6
France	8.7	5.6	38.5	n.a.	88.6	6.7
Germany	10.5	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	83.7	7.6
Greece	10.3	6.9	n.a.	n.a.	59.1	2.6
Italy	9.3	9.6	n.a.	n.a.	64.6	3.8
Netherlands	13.5	n.a.	46.8	n.a.	92.8	9.1
Spain	11.3	13.6	27.1	26.6	90.0	2.3
Portugal	-	-	-	89.0	-	-

The seasonability of biomass poses additional challenges. Biorefineries, to maximize the return on investment, need to operate all year-round. This means that not only enough biomass should be available, but also diversified and integrated logistics systems are required to supply needed types of biomass even out of season at both local and regional levels. Additionally, long-term supply has to guarantee delivery at an acceptable cost and quality. In bio-based industries, the process chains of food crops have been optimizing over a long time. Hence, the utilization is very efficient. Additionally, the by-products are used in food and feed. Biorefineries for food crops have existed for many years. All parts of the harvested crops are converted into food, feed, materials, and energy. Apart from the biorefineries, logistics and processes (varieties, cultivation, harvest, storage, quality control) for food crops are well established.

Rabobank in their analysis of the Dutch plastics packaging industry provides an overview of plastic production costs' distribution (Figure 6) that can serve as a basis when calculation production costs for bioplastics. Raw materials are the most important part of production costs. Of course, differences between companies and in time exist. Labor costs depend on wages and on number of employees per tonne of output. The last one due to technological progress is expected to decrease in time. Energy costs are related to energy prices and efficiency of production technologies.

Figure 6. Distribution of plastic production costs

Source: <https://www.vmt.nl/Nieuws/~media/0009DEF665C6266E16E81EE77B75C006.ashx>

A comparison of cost distribution for plastic bottle production in different countries/regions is given in Figure 7. Two intermediary products are used for PET production for plastic bottles: para-xylenes (made from naphtha) and ethylene (made from ethane (US and Middle East) and naphtha (China, EU Japan)). Prices for naphtha are fairly similar across regions, since it is a globally traded commodity. Prices for feedstock used for ethylene production differ significantly. After the Middle East, US has the lowest ethane prices in the world. EU, China, and Japan have to rely mostly on expensive naphtha. These price differences result in price range starting from 1.7 cents per bottle in Middle East to 3.7 cents per bottle in Japan (IEA, 2014).

Figure 7: Estimated unit production costs distribution of plastic bottle

Figure 8. Production costs of plastic bottle (cents)

FAOSTAT also provides data on producer prices on selected crops and countries (Table 19). Also, data in some countries are not available. This information could be a good basis for companies when estimating the domestic availability of crops and economic benefits of importing feedstock. Thus, according to the latest data (2017), the highest price for corn was assigned to Italy (213.4 \$/tonne), whereas the lowest one belonged to France (160.9 \$/tonne). Italy is a leading EU country in artichoke production (Table 18), however, a price is not available for this country. Spain had the lowest price (751.7 \$/tonne). Much higher price for artichoke in 2017 belongs to Greece (1372.7 \$/tonne). Data on producer prices for chicory roots is also scarce and available only for Belgium, Greece, and Spain ranging from 572.1 to 897.3 \$/tonne. In terms of producer prices, production of sugar beet is the most economically viable in Belgium (24.9 \$/tonne); the highest price

was assigned to Spain (45.9 \$/tonne). Producers' prices for wheat also differ among countries being the lowest in France (157.7 \$/tonne) and the highest in Spain (\$/tonne).

Table 19. Producer prices for selected crops, 2017 (\$/tonne)

Country	Feedstock					
	Corn	Artichoke	Chicory roots	Sugar cane	Sugar beet	Wheat
Belgium	n.a.	n.a.	572.1	n.a.	24.9	159.3
France	160.9	969.2	n.a.	n.a.	29.1	157.7
Germany	176.9	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	33.8	170.2
Greece	231.5	1372.7	696.3	n.a.	29.2	218.8
Italy	213.4	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	211.5
Netherlands	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	37.0	173.6
Spain	193.6	751.7	897.3	394.4	45.9	208.6
Portugal	-	-	-	304.3	-	-

In their publication, Prospects for Agricultural Markets in the EU 2018-2030, European Commission claims that a gap between agricultural EU and world prices decreased from 30-40 % to 10 % during the last ten years. In 2017 this gap accounted for 13 %. In addition to that, price volatility for grains has been decreasing starting from 2009. In the years 2015-2017, it was characterized by more stable prices at lower levels. Figure 9 provides data on the development of corn prices comparing EU and world markets with projections to 2030. Also, market analysts predict a decreasing gap between EU and world prices during the next few years, starting from 2022 a gap will be slowly increasing again.

Figure 9. Corn market prices with predictions

As a comparison to renewable feedstock, a market overview of the crude oil used for the production of fossil-based plastics is provided below. The use of food crops for bioplastics production is subject to high volatility of the raw material prices. In case of food crisis, the level of prices will be quite high, since it is directly linked to food and feed prices. At the same time, prices for crude oil are also subjected to variations. Constantly changing conditions make the oil prices to fluctuate. European Commission, based on OECD and HIS Markit, predicts more stable crude oil prices until 2027 having an increase after (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Average annual world crude oil price with price assumption (\$/barrel)

Source: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/food-farming-fisheries/farming/documents/medium-term-outlook-2018-report_en.pdf

Since summer 2017, oil price has been rising due to a continued world economic growth. In addition, since 2017, oil supply has been tight due to the OPEC members’ agreement to cut production. A situation became more complex in 2018, particularly after the US sanctions against Iran. Up to 2030, world oil demand is projected to grow and the market is assumed to remain balanced. Also, some experts predict new suppliers of petroleum entering the market that could lead to less costly petroleum-based plastics.

Plastics ‘yielding’ also influences the end price of the product. According to estimations (Figure 11), between 6 to 7 barrels are needed to produce a tonne of fossil-based resins. On the contrary, the efficiency of feedstock for bioplastics is measured in kg (Table 20). The table shows that the output of bioplastics varies depending on the type of feedstock.

Figure 11. Quantity of barrels of crude oil in the form of feedstock (barrel/tonne of resins)

Table 20. Feedstock efficiency (kg)

Bioplastics	Feedstock	Feedstock efficiency, (per 1 kg of bioplastics)
PE	Sugar cane	27.5
	Sugar beet	23.92
	Wheat	6.84
PET	Sugar cane	5.47
	Molasses cane	1.85
	Wheat	4.41
	Corn	3.25
	Poplar	5.05
PLA	Corn starch	1.53
	Cassava	4.42
PUR	Palm oil	0.66
	Corn starch	1.44
PP	Sugar cane	34.94
PVC	Sugar beet	12.62

Conversion of the raw materials to intermediate products and then to the final bioplastic is an important step influencing the end price. Data on the prices for intermediate products for PEF production is very limited since this bioplastic is not present on the market yet. The information that is available is described below. Information on Mater-Bi production is subjected to intellectual property rights and could not be disclosed.

Of course, there are some product's end price components, which apply to any plastic production. Thus, Eurostat provides statistics on electricity prices. Figure 12 gives an overview of how electricity prices differ among selected countries. In 2018, Germany, Belgium, and Spain had the highest prices (0.295, 0.273 and 0.238 €/kWh respectively) compared to other countries. The lowest electricity prices belonged to the Netherland (0.171 €/kWh) and France (0.175 €/kWh).

Figure 12: Electricity prices for selected countries, 2018 (€/kWh)

Polyethylene furandicarboxylate (PEF) is biobased plastic that is considered to be an alternative to the polyethylene terephthalate (PET), - a fossil-based plastic. A purified terephthalic acid (PTA) is the main component of PET. It could be replaced by biobased 2,5-furandicarboxylic acid (FDCA) that is used in the

production of PEF and made from renewable resources. FDCA is produced from 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF). This organic compound could significantly contribute to the transition from petrochemical-based production to biobased carbohydrate production. A simplified PEF production flowchart is given in Figure 13.

Figure 13. PEF production flowchart

Since the scope of HMF and FDCA production is limited, data on their market development is restricted or not available. There are several studies about market overview and projections for these chemicals present; however, they are not in open access. Due to the financial limitations of this project, it was not possible to get that data. Below a short description of prices and market situation is provided.

In 2013 there was a study published in Computer & Chemicals Engineering Journal, in which researchers offered two alternative processes for converting HMF to FDCA using simulations. Also, an economic analysis was done. An estimation of the costs' division is given in Figure 14.

Scientists claim that 19 % of the total annual costs of the process catalyst cost makes up. This is due to the high acquisition cost of catalysts. According to the calculation, decreasing its cost by half can reduce the minimum sale price of FDCA by 7.79 %. Its doubling increases the final FDCA price by 15.58 %.

The biggest share of the annual cost belongs to HMF – 39 %. Hence, the FDCA production cost is hugely impacted by the price of HMF. Experts assume that to cover an expected demand large quantities of the FDCA will be needed. As a result, a large scale production of HMF is necessary. The economics of the FDCA production is predicted to be impacted much by the new routes for a large scale conversion of cellulosic biomass to HMF that would be economically efficient.

Figure 14. Annual costs of the production process of FDCA

An impact of raw materials market prices on the final price of FDCA is presented in Figure 15. Data shows that the market price of FDCA is increased by 88 \$/tonne by increasing oxygen market price from 250 \$/tonne to 500 \$/tonne. Reduction in Acetic acid price from 550 \$/tonne to 400 \$/tonne reduced FDCA market price by 15 \$/tonne. A minimum sale price of FDCA (1936 \$/tonne) could be reached if a market price of HMF is decreased to 500 \$/tonne. Even though an HMF price range in this study differs between 500-1070 \$/tonne, a study published in 2012 in Energy & Environmental Science Journal provides totally different value indicating price for HMF+HMF ethers to be 1175 €/tonne. Final report of the project From the Sugar Platform to biofuels and biochemical published in 2015, estimates price of HMF to be higher than 2655 \$/tonne (price for FDCA is described as not available, high). Also, scientists claim that the minimum sale price of FDCA can be reduced by 4.7 % when doubling plant capacity, and by 19.3 % if the plant is three times larger. This is an obvious indication of the importance of the economy of scale. Despite the fact that current study assumes a price range for FDCA to be roughly between 1900-2700 \$/tonne, this is anyway higher than the market price of Purified Terephthalic Acid.

Figure 15. Minimum sale price of FDCA as a function of raw material market prices (\$/tonne)

Source: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0098135412003961>

Purified Terephthalic Acid is a very important raw material. It is widely used for production PET, PTT, and PBT. The last data provided by Plastics Insight about the global market of PTA is provided by plasticsinsights.com. A continuous rise in production of PTA is explained by an increasing demand from polyester fiber maker as well as from construction, electronics, textiles, beverages and packaging sectors. The amount of produced PTA in 2016 accounted for 61.2 million tonnes that is 13.3 million tonnes more than in 2014. The production capacity of PTA has raised from 71 million tonnes in 2014 to 80 million tonnes in 2016 (Figure 16). Imports of PTA to the EU amounted to 72.281 tonnes in July 2018. South Korea and Mexico were the main importers.

Figure 16. Global production of PTA (million tonnes)

Figure 17 shows price fluctuations for PTA within the year 2017. The highest prices were recorded for Russia (max. 1460\$/tonne in December), India (max. 1410 \$/tonne in April) and China (max. 1400 \$/tonne in March). The lowest prices for PTA in 2017 belonged to Japan (in a range 660-740 \$/tonne) and Germany (in a range 663-757 \$/tonne).

Figure 17. World trading prices for PTA, 2017 (\$/tonne)

Asia-Pacific region had 77 % of the total market share in 2016. 57 % were held by China. The total market demand for PTA in 2016 accounted for 77.5 million tonnes. Europe had a share of only 6 % (4.65 million tonnes). Polyester fibers made up 65 % of the global PTA demand in 2016, followed by PET bottles resins (27 %) and films (8 %) (Figure 18).

Figure 18. Global PTA demand by application, 2016

Adipic acid is another alternative that could be potentially replaced by the FDCA. In 2015 the Invista plant in Texas, which had supplied Europe with the Adipic acid, was closed. A reduction of effective capacity occurred

also in Europe after BASF has retired one of its lines at Ludwigshafen complex (from 260.000 to 210.000 tonnes/year). LANXESS (Germany) is trying to improve its production capacity but it cannot compensate totally the exit of BASF's 50.000 tonnes/year. Over the year 2016, there was a big gap in import volumes due to a large deficit between the EU and the rest of the world. In addition, materials from China have become scarce, whereas European demand is growing. Production capacities of the Adipic acid in Europe are given by ICIS and provided in Figure 19.

Figure 19. Europe Adipic Acid Production capacity (1,000 tonnes/year)

Prices for the Adipic acid during 2015-2016 were driven principally by feedstock cost movements. Freely negotiated values have decoupled from feedstock numbers in late 2016 – in early 2017 (from about 1550 €/tonne in April 2016 to about 2250 €/tonne in March 2017). The European market continues to feel a supply crunch having volumes difficult to be secured.

In 2017, the global revenue value of the HMF market was \$ 55.867,000. It is expected to reach \$ 62.700,000 by 2025. A compound annual growth rate of global revenue is projected to be 1.45 %. The world's largest export volume and manufacturer of HMF market belong to Europe. According to the data of 2017, China is the second-largest market. In recent years Ava Biochem made the most profit having 82.03 % of market share. Second and Third places took Robinson Brothers (4.45 %) and Penta Manufacturer (3.57 %). Due to different strategies, the market share gap is constantly expanding. Out of the two main types of HMS (industrial and food grade), industrial-grade sales volume was about 34.086 kg in 2017 (72.11 % of global sales).

According to the data of 2014, the application segments for FDCA were PET (64 % of the global market by 2020) and polyamides (80.000 tonnes by 2020). In general, the addressable FDCA market after PTA replacement could reach 50 million tonnes. As of 2018, it is estimated that by 2023 the FDCA market potential would be 498.000 tonnes accounting for 435 million €.

End of life options for bioplastics arise new problems. Bioplastics recycling can cause additional costs. It is difficult to separate bioplastics from plastics. Concerns about end of life challenges are expressed by the plastics converters industry. Sorting between recyclable and non-recyclable, bio-based and petroleum-based

and mixed-source plastics brings additional expenses and difficulties affecting recycled material quality and impairing the already low level of plastics recycling. Increasing the quantity of biodegradable plastics that enter separating streams, would higher the collection costs since expensive adjustments in waste collection would be required.

In addition, consumers have to understand that compostable plastic does not automatically mean biodegradable. Industrial composting facilities are not the backyard composters. Some scientists speak out negatively about compostability. They see it as a “negative step” during which precious resources such as land and energy are wasted for a single-use product that, in the end, will not turn into nutrient-rich soil as at the beginning. Also, producers have to ensure that compostable plastic does not bring toxic chemicals into soil.

Both technologies in question have different end of life options. Mater-Bi is biodegradable and compostable. It can be recycled together with organic waste without having to separate the contents. PEF is recyclable (thermal or enzyme-based recycling). Table 21 presents data on the costs of end of life for packaging. Country and type of end of life options should be considered when calculating technology costs of bioplastics. Thus, for example in Germany, costs of recycling depend on materials, and collecting and sorting arise additional costs. In France and the Netherlands, collecting and sorting are combined in one price. Costs for landfilling vary greatly among countries. In Germany landfilling is not possible for packaging. Information about some countries is not available.

Table 21. End of life costs (€/tonne)

Technology	Belgium	France	Germany	Italy	Netherlands
Combustion			35-90		
Home composting			0	0	
Industrial composting			ca. 46	80	
Collection	235	867*	139	269-378	817*
Sorting	157	0*	60-100	80	0*
Recycling			30-80**	179-228****	
Landfilling***	Flanders: - combustible waste: 101.91 - non-combustible waste: 56.05 Wallonia: 113.01 Brussels: not possible	Authorized landfills: 23-40 Non-authorized landfills: 150	not possible for packaging	Depending on the region: 5.2-25.82. Not possible for packaging	

*Collection and sorting together

** depends on material, e. g. film, mixed plastics

*** (tax) municipal solid waste

**** depends: slot A (selectable and recyclable packaging from trade and industry circuit): € 179.00 / t

slot B (selectable and recyclable packaging from domestic circuit): € 208.00 / t

slot C (packaging that can not be selected/recycled to current state of technology): € 228.00 / t

7.3.2 Market data

According to the European Bioplastics, 2.11 million tonnes of bioplastics were produced globally in 2018 (Figure 20). Shares of bioplastics are projected to increase over the years reaching 2.62 million tonnes in 2023. 57 % of new economy bioplastics were biodegradable in 2018. It is estimated that in 2023,

biodegradable plastics will represent only 51 %. However, it does not mean that there will a decrease in production. Biodegradability seems to be an optimistic scenario for the end of life options. Despite this fact, one should consider that there are different types of biodegradability. Even though a product is claimed to be biodegradable, its end of life depends where the item ends up. For example, if bioplastics ends up in the ocean, the process of biodegradability might not start. Also, biodegradability does not necessarily imply that the process will take place in a short period of time. In this case, industrial composting might be an appropriate option; however, it is difficult to realize due to a lack of needed facilities. As a result, biodegradable plastics are most often sent to landfills or incinerators.

Figure 20. Global production capacities of bioplastics with projections (1,000 tonnes)

In the field of biodegradable plastics, PLA and PHAs are the main growth drivers (Figure 21). PHAs were in development for a while and now enter the market at a commercial scale. Their production is estimated to quadruple in the next five years. Compared to 2018, the production of PLA is projected to grow by 60 % by 2023.

Around 48 % of the global bioplastics production capacities belong to bio-based PET and bio-based PA. New capacities of bio-PE are planned to come online in Europe during the next years that would increase its production scope. Predictions made regarding the production of bio-PET were not realized since the focus has shifted to the development of PEF that is expected to enter the market in 2023. Also, bio-based PP is predicted to enter the market on the industrial scale in 2023 with strong potentials due to its wide possible application range. On the figure, plastics marked with solid fill belong to biodegradable, whereas others are bio-based but non-biodegradable.

*are projected to enter the market on industrial scale

Figure 21. Global production capacities of bioplastics by material type, 2018 (%)

The latest available data on the production capacities of bioplastics in Europe was published in 2016 (Figure 22). An important point to mention is the appearance of PEF with its increasing production over the years. At the time of this publication, an industrial production of PEF was predicted to start in 2018-2019. As can be seen from the latest available data, the start of PEF massive production has been shifted to 2023.

Figure 22. Bio-based polymers: Evolution of production capacities in Europe (million tonnes/year)

Source: http://www.bio-based.eu/market_study/media/16-12-16-Bio-based-Building-Blocks-and-Polymers-short-version.pdf

There is an increasing number of markets, where bioplastics are applied (Figure 23). Packaging remains the largest niche for bioplastics taking almost 65 % of the total bioplastics market (in 2018).

The textile industry has a quite high share of bio-based fibers. The fast-growing demand for products is the main driver. Calculations show a gap in textile fiber of about 150 million tonnes until the year 2050. If petrochemical fibers do not fill the gap, bio-based polymer fibers could improve the situation only with huge investments directed into their development. An additional increase in demand for bio-based and biodegradable textiles can be caused by a microplastic problem (accumulation of small fibers in the environment released by washing machines).

There are several factors driving the application of new materials in the automotive sector, such as costs, price competitiveness, lightweight construction, special properties, and environmental footprint. Thus, being only bio-based has no power for the automobile market and does not impact sales. With improved properties and cost reduction in processing only a small increase in bio-based materials application is expected in this industry. A huge impact could be reached with an introduction to the supportive framework conditions. Also, the development could speed up in case the oil prices increase

Figure 23. Global production capacities of bioplastics by market segment, 2018 (1,000 tonnes)

Source: <https://www.european-bioplastics.org/market>

In general, the information on the application of bioplastics and its potential influence on the automotive market in the EU is very limited and no reports for the past years are available. Experts explain this situation with the fact that the automotive sector does not see itself as a part of the bio-based industry and there are no targets to increase a share of bio-based products. Additionally, this is a very secretive group. Only a few producers are willing to share data. There are no official statistics available.

Despite a wide variety of alternative markets, experts postulate that there is a lack of market for reused plastics that possesses an additional problem. Application options of reused plastics are limited due to the fact that blends of different polymers coming from various packaging products are likely to have inferior properties compared to their origins. Thus, legally recycled plastics cannot be used for packaging food. Less quality applications should be found. This, in turn, implies that for bioplastics production new feedstock will always be required. A research directed towards adding functionality and new properties to bio-based plastics would enable to open the market further.

Table 22 provides a list of possible markets, where investigated technologies (Mater-Bi and PEF) have the potentials to be applied.

Table 22. Privileged markets for Mater-Bi and PEF

Technology	Privileged markets
Mater-Bi	Films: shopping bags, bags for separated waste collection, food packaging, films for mulching; thermoformed articles: tubs and rigid containers for foods, compostable pots for nursery gardening; additives: biofiller; expanded plastics: packaging, Loose fillers that have excellent shock-absorbing properties; extruded products: cotton buds, drinking straws, flexible pipes for agriculture; injection moulded products: disposable cutlery, pens, combs, toys
PEF	O2 sensitive drinks (beer, juice, etc.), carbonated drinks (smaller serving size), water bottles, lighter bottles, hot fill applications, fibers (apparels, carpets, home furnishing, disposables commodities, fabrics, diapers, filters, and industrial fibers), films

Grandviewresearch.com in their research presented in 2018, provides insights into the PEF market. Some indicators are available in open access. Thus, in 2016, the global PEF market volume was estimated as followed: around 48 % belonged to Asia Pacific, Europe's share accounted for about 23 %, North America had around 18 %, and about 11 % belonged to the rest of the world (Figure 24).

Figure 24. Global PEF market volume by region, 2016

As of 2018, an estimated PEF global market demand reached 11.700 tonnes in 2016 were evaluated in € 18.5 million and is projected to be about 16.640 tonnes in 2022. An expected global CAGR from 2018 to 2022 is 8.8 %; in Europe – 7.0 %. According to the predictions made in 2016, 44 % of the overall market revenue of PEF will belong to fibers that will be the largest application segment in 2022.

Mater-Bi is a range of innovative products consisting of 25 types of materials. Data scarcity on market volumes, prices, etc. is explained by confidentiality and intellectual property rights. General assumptions about the prices for Mater-Bi conclude that the price level for these products is 2-3 times higher than other bioplastics and is highly related to the end product. Thus, macroeconomic environment for this technology could be considered only in terms of biodegradable and compostable plastics market development.

Table 23 and Figure 25 provides an overview of market prices for bioplastics and fossil-based plastics (Wageningen Fodd & Biobased Research Institute). Definitely, the aim to replace conventional plastics is a difficult task in the current stages. The end price of bioplastics is one of the main macroeconomic barriers that hugely affect the market. Different studies report on 20 to 100 % higher prices for bioplastics compared to petrochemical plastics. Moreover, the production chain of plastics has been very efficient for decades, whereas the bioplastic sector requires big investments.

A high competition with fossil-based plastics is also complicated by the fact that they are not required to display sustainability.

Table 23. Price level for bioplastics, 2016 (€/kg)

Plastic	Price level	Plastic	Price level
CA	5	PBAT	3.5
Bio-PA	+10-20 %	Bio-PBS	4
Bio-PE	+10-40 %	PHA	5
Bio-PET	n.a.	PLA	2
Bio-PP	+10-100 %	PTT	4
PP (certified bio)	+40-50 %	Starch blends	2-4

Figure 25. Price level for fossil-based plastics, 2016 (€/tonne)

Nova Institute has published a study in 2015 providing a global number of producers of different types of bioplastic with an estimation of each plastic type availability (Table 24).

Table 24. Availability of bio-based and biodegradable plastics as experienced by WFBR and global number of producers per type of bioplastic

Polymer type	Number of producers, 2013	Availability, 2016
CA	17	Good
Bio-PA	9	Good
Bio-PE	1	Sufficient
Bio-PET	5	No experience
PBAT	4	Sufficient
PBS	10	Sufficient
PHA	14	Poor
PLA	28	Good
Starch blends	15	Sufficient

Figure 26 presents shares of plastics applications in different sectors. The packaging industry remains leading for the application of PE, PP, PS, and PET. PE is mostly used for reusable bags, trays, and containers, agricultural film, food packaging film, milk bottles, shampoo bottles, etc. PP is applied widely for food packaging, sweet and snack wrappers, hinged caps, microwave containers, pipes, and others. PS is used for plastic cups, egg trays, etc. Application of PET include bottles for water, soft drinks, juices, cleaners, and others.

Figure 26. European plastics converter demand by segments and polymer types, 2016

Source: https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=2&ved=2ahUKEwix9pXr_YPgAhXN-6QKHYO4BPwQFjABegQICBAC&url=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.plasticseurope.org%2Fdownload_file%2Fforce%2F1830%2F181&usq=AOvVaw3xFjxBhtKek83cdfP6Hw0S

Market of PET is of high interest since this plastic is the main competitor for PEF. The situation on the European market during the first half of 2018 shows a rapid price increase (Figure 27). Due to unprecedented tightness price has jumped by 30 %. Such situation was stimulated by a heavily contracted environment in Europe and a number of not planned shutdowns globally. The market situation is characterized as dry. Such sort of prices appeared last time only in 2012. However, at that period prices for raw materials and crude oil were much higher.

Figure 27. European market price for PET, 2018 (€/tonne)

In 2016, the global PET market was evaluated at \$23.891 million. It is predicted to reach \$38.014 million by 2023 at CAGR of 6.9% in the a period 2017-2023. The packaging segment is expected to have a CAGR of 7.1 % during these years. However, rising strict environmental regulations substitutes entering the market are assumed to affect the PET market growth. More than 30 % share of the total revenue in 2016 accounted for Asia-Pacific that was followed by Europe and North America.

Synvina is one of the main competitors for PEF production. It is a joint venture between BASF (Germany) and Avantium (Netherlands) that was founded in 2016 with the aim to produce and market FDCA and PEF. It is located in Amsterdam. The main goal of the company is to develop a complete supply chain for PEF. Synvina will continue Avantium’s establishes partnership activities. In 2015 there was a partnership signed with Mitsui. Companies will work on the development of PEF bottles and thin films in Japan. According to the agreement signed in 2016, with a Japanese company Toyobo, they will work on PEF polymerization for further development of thin PEF films. This film is claimed to have better properties compared to standard PEF films that would enable new packaging opportunities (for example, transparent pouches for sous, etc.). Also, Synvina will continue to cooperate with the Coca-Cola Company, Danone, ALPLA and others on the Joint Development Platform for PEF bottles.

A planned potential for FDCA annual production consists of 50.000 tonnes. However, there was an extension of the pilot phase. Currently, the first commercialization is planned to start in 2023-2024. The information appeared in social media in October, 2018 claims that Avantium and BASF are having a dispute about the future of their venture due to the disagreement between companies on the timing for the fulfillment of the criteria to invest in an industrial-scale plant for FDCA. At the same time, the Technical Committee of the European PET Bottle Platform gave Synvina an interim approval for the recyclability of Synvina’s PEF bottles

in the PET streams (with an applied PEF market penetration of up to 2 %). This approval is valid until June, 2020.

An alternative product that could become a competitor for PEF, is a 100-% biobased PlantBottle produced by The Coca-Cola Company. In 2015 its prototype was already presented at the World Expo in Milan. It is still being under development and improvement, but the main aim of the company is to replace all its petroleum-based PET bottles by 2020.

PEF continues to attract interest among scientists and alternative research on FDCA and PEF is being conducted. Thus, in July, 2018, an article in social media presented the information that chemists from the Ruhr-Universität Bochum have developed a new, low-cost catalyst for FDCA production. In August, 2018, another article revealed the information that a team from the ETH Zurich University has improved a method of PEF production drastically. Currently, in a cooperation with Sulzer Company they are trying to implement the method at industrial level. An increased attention to PEF technology might attract new investors that could increase competition. According to the Morgan Stanley Institute for Sustainable Investing, about 75 % of investors (based on questionnaires) are interested in sustainable investing. Their interest is also driven by an increased interest of consumers in sustainable products.

Another alternative competitor to PEF is a new bio-copolyester developed by a South Korean company SK Chemicals Company (2018) as a replacement for PET. It is called Ecozen HF and claimed to be made out of renewable materials and be recyclable. According to the provided information, this product has processing requirements similar to PET so that it can be used in the same moulding processes. Ecozen HF is fully miscible with PET in the recycling streams. This simplifies product's introduction to the market since needed infrastructure already exists. In addition to that, Ecozen HF has lower transportation costs. In cooperation with a distribution company VELOX, SK Chemicals Company is aimed to distribute Ecozen HF in nearly all European countries.

7.3.3 Industry data

According to the European Plastics Converters, a turnover in the European plastics industry reaches € 362 billion (Figure 28). Manufacturers make up around € 100 billion. Converters create around € 260 billion. The rest – ca. € 2 billion are generated by recyclers.

Around 53.000 companies are involved in the European plastics industry (Figure 29). 94.34 % of them belong to converters. A share of manufacturers consists of 3.77 %. 1.89 % of companies are a part of the recycling sector.

European plastics industry employs ca. 1.770.000 people. 90.40 % of them are working for the plastics converting sector, 7.91 % are involved in manufacturing, and 1.69 % are employed by recycling companies.

Figure 28: Turnover in the European plastics industry

Figure 29. Companies in the European plastics industry

Market of biopolymers continues to grow. According to predictions, from the year 2013 to 2020 production capacity for bio-based polymers will triple (from 5.1 to 17 million tonnes). In 2013, a turnover of bio-based polymers accounted for € 10 billion worldwide. Compared to petrochemical polymers, which have a CAGR of 3-4 %, CAGR of bio-based polymers reaches almost 20 %.

In 2017 the global bioplastics market was evaluated at \$ 21.126,31 million. It is expected to reach \$ 68.577,25 million by 2024 having a CAGR of 18,8 % in a period of 2018-2024.

European transition towards circular economy is considered an important factor contributing to job creation and generating new employment opportunities. In 2012, according to the WRAP study, 3.38 million people were employed in the EU in the circular economy. The results of three scenario tests are also provided (Table 25). This table shows that current circular economy activities could potentially generate more than 1 million jobs over the EU by 2030. In case of further “transformations” in the circular economy about 3 million new jobs in the EU could appear.

Table 25. Annual increase in jobs (gross) from expanding circular economy activity to 2030 across EU

Scenario	Increase in jobs (gross)
No new initiatives	251.000

Current development	1.191.000
Transformation	2.941.000

An established value chain is inevitable for a product to reach end users. The bio-based plastics value chain starts with a feedstock supplier followed by a polymer production. It can be direct (e.g. PHA) or through an intermediate step during which a monomer is formed (e.g. PLA). At the next step – compound formulation – plastic properties are modified. This process is followed by conversion. The value chain final steps consist of a brand owner, a retailer, and consumers. Waste management eventually closes the chain.

Figure 30. Bioplastics value chain

No single enterprise can provide the scale that is needed for a product to be commercialized. Novel biopolymers' production is complicated due to the absence of established infrastructure. This imposes additional challenges. Compatibility of the biopolymer with processing equipment through the whole value chain is a necessary option in order for a biopolymer to be taken into production. Also, companies need to get advantages over conventional plastic production (superior properties, cost advantages etc.). Brand owner takes the highest risks and is the main decision-maker. The key point for the brand owner is to understand the value of the product.

7.3.3 Circular economy – new plastics economy

A lot of scientists are working on the development of new bioplastics. However, a long transition way from the theory to practice has to be overcome. Taking into account current technological capacities, it is not easy to jump directly into the production of new bioplastics. R&D and innovations are slowed down by a lack of cooperation and knowledge exchange between parties of the value chain. Significant R&D efforts are needed. Large investments have to be directed towards the construction of new production plants. Increasing the efficiency of biomass processing might become a big advantage of bioplastics production; a lack of modern industrial biotechnologies can make a smooth expansion difficult. Additional investments will be needed in the future into the enlargement of arable land.

Another topic is the certification of bioplastics. Time, money and effort may hamper the certification process. The application of voluntarily standards cannot solve the problem as it cannot be totally monitored nor enforced. This means that standards can be misused.

Existence of different labels can make consumers to be unsure of what to do with bioplastic. As a result, if a packaging ends up in the wrong place, it will cause damage, not a benefit. For example, in case of separate recycling streams, the entire lot can be rejected, if contaminated with inappropriate plastic.

A significant barrier that exists throughout the countries is an insecure political framework. This brings the EU into a weak position making it suffering from underinvestments by the private sector.

In December, 2015 the EU Action Plan for the Circular Economy was adopted. Also, in December, 2017 new rules on waste found agreement. According to them, a new target of 55 % recycling of plastic packaging waste by 2020 was fixed. By 2030, only recyclable or reusable plastic should be produced. To reach this goal, the Commission will work on adopting legislative requirements.

Major investments in both infrastructure and innovation will be necessary to achieve the goals. Estimated additional investments lie between € 8.4 and € 16.6 billion. Thus, a central task for this strategy to create a proper framework for investment and innovation. Fully biodegradable in seawater and freshwater materials are of a particular attraction for the Commission. Attention is also put to research on alternative feedstock, including bio-based feedstock. The development of alternative feedstock for plastic production will be supported.

So far, over € 250 million were provided by Horizon 2020 to finance R&D in the areas related to the strategy. About half of this money was directed for alternative feedstock development. An additional € 100 million will be invested in financing priority measures (enhancing recycling processes efficiency, developing smarter plastic materials, tracing and removing hazardous contaminants from recycled plastics).

Another topic is private and public investment, which share has to be increased in order to reach strategy implementation. Currently, uncertainties about profitability are holding back investments. In France, for example, only two-thirds of the plastics recycling businesses are profitable. To make plastics recycling economically viable, modernization and scaling up of the recycling plants are needed. A contribution to developing EU recycling capacity is also done by the European Structural and Investments Funds. From 2014 to 2020, over € 5.5 billion were provided for waste management improvement activities.

8. Further work to be done

Next steps of the work will be:

- To finish the expression of questioners and associate them to references, in order to help the user to refer to initial documents
- To incorporate results of specifications from other work packages (consumer acceptability and LCA)
- To propose ponderations to each specification listed; In that way, scores of “accessibility and success on the market” will be possibly calculated (ACTIA wants to deliver this as a software); an illustration is given below concerning retailer specifications :

	critical property	values	values or remarks	score	score de référence	coeffic
1						
2						
3	product sold in heterogeneous pallet ?	yes /no	yes	5		5
4	optimized for euro palet 80 120 ?	yes /no	not relevant	0		1
5	need of intercalation sheets ?	yes /no	yes	0		1
6	need of stretch palletising film ?	yes /no	no	0		1
7	non self supporting product (or secondary packed product) ?	yes /no	I don't know	0		1
8	self supporting product (or secondary packed product)?	yes /no	not relevant	0		1
9	resistance to vibrations tested ?	yes /no	not relevant	0		1
10						
11						1

Figure 31: Illustration of retailer specifications

For each item of the checklist the user will have the possibility to give either:

- Answers leading to an increase of the score (2 possibilities : maximum increase if the evaluation was done and led to positive result, and lower score if the evaluation was done but with a negative result)
- Answers leading to a zero score
- The possibility to consider the item is “not relevant”.

At the end, the score will be express in the following form:

global score	total	max (including "not relevant")
20	30	42

20 points score for a total of 30, considering the items considered as “relevant” by the auto-evaluator, but then 12 points associated to items considered as “non relevant” by the auto-evaluator.

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10. Annexes

Table 26: Technologies of MyPack project

Technology code / Industrial partner involved / Starting TRL	Technology	Project objective concerned	Illustration
TEC1 NOVAMONT TRL 6-7	Bio-based and biodegradable materials and multilayer film technology	Obj 1.1 and 1.2	
TEC2 PIMM TRL7	High oxygen barrier packaging by microlayer multiplication technology, and by replacing EVOH by PA	Obj 2	
TEC3 NATUREPLAST TRL8	Heat Resistant PLA (rigid packaging)	Obj 1.2	
	and Soften PLA (film applications)		
TEC4 UNIBAS TRL7	Microtechnology insertion conferring breathing properties	Obj 2	

<p>TEC5 FURSTGROUP TRL8</p>	<p>SiOx barrier inert</p>	<p>Obj 2</p>	
<p>TEC6 WIPAK TRL6</p>	<p>Antimicrobial packaging</p>	<p>Obj 2</p>	
<p>TEC 7 UHOH TRL5</p>	<p>PEF renewable substitute of PET</p>	<p>Obj 1.2</p>	<p><i>PEF vs PET: Same or <u>new</u> market ?</i></p>